

D6.1

Market and actor-role analysis

PoDIUM

PDI connectivity and cooperation enablers building trust and sustainability for CCAM

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
ADAS	Advanced Driver Assistance Systems
AHP	Analytic Hierarchy Process
ATMC	Automated Traffic Management Centers
AV	Autonomous Vehicle
AWS	Amazon Web Services
B2B	Business-to-Business
B2C	Business to Customer
CAGR	Compound Annual Growth Rate
CAMV	Connected and Autonomous Mobility Vehicles
CAV	Connected Autonomous Vehicle
CCAM	Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility
CI	Consistency Index
C-ITS	Cooperative Intelligent Transport System
CPM	Cooperative Perception Messages
CR	Consistency Ratio
CV	Connected Vehicle
C-V2X	Cooperative Vehicle-to-Everything
DENM	Decentralized Environmental Notification Message
DSRC	Dedicated Short-Range Communications
DT	Digital Twins
eMBB	enhanced Mobile Broadband
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EV	Emergency Vehicles
EVP	Emergency Vehicle Preemption
EU	European Commission
FCC	Federal Communications Commission
FCD	Floating Car Data
FR	Frequency Range

GPS	Global Positioning System
HW	Hardware
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
ITS	Intelligent Transport System
KER	Key Exploitable Result
LTE	Long Term Evolution
M2M	Machine-to-Machine
MaaS	Mobility-as-a-Service
MCM	Manoeuvre Coordination Message
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
mMTC	massive Machine Type Communications
MNO	Mobile Network Operator
OBU	On-Board Unit
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
OTT	Over-The-Top
PDI	Physical and Digital Infrastructure
RFID	Radio Frequency Identification
RSU	Road-Side Unit
RU	Road User
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
SW	Software
TGC	Trusted Computing Group
TIM	Traffic Incident Management
TMC	Traffic Management Centre
TPM	Trusted Platform Module
TSP	Transit Signal Priority
UC	Use Case
URLLC	Ultra-Reliable Low Latency communications
V2I	Vehicle-to-Infrastructure
V2V	Vehicle-to-Vehicle

V2X	Vehicle-to-Everything
VSWG	Vehicle Service working Group
VRU	Vulnerable Road User

Executive Summary

This deliverable investigates the business aspects of the PoDIUM solutions. Towards this direction, three different types of activities are performed: market analysis, definition of PoDIUM's ecosystem and roadmapping.

The first step in this endeavour is to assess the current status of the market for each PoDIUM component through a market analysis. For each component, the same extensive set of data is provided; among others market size and growth, as well as the factors contributing to the potential growth of the market. Information about market players and competitive products is also included. The fact that all the studies from market research firms forecast significant growth in all the relevant markets is very promising for the potential impact of PoDIUM.

Regarding the ecosystem, the PoDIUM platform roles are identified, and the interactions among them are presented in the defined reference model. The incentives and benefits from the PoDIUM platform are identified for each role in the ecosystem.

Regarding the road-mapping activity, the factors affecting market adoption and evolution of PoDIUM solutions are identified and assessed by experts using the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP). A survey is conducted to evaluate the relative importance of these factors and prioritise them. The survey has been correctly completed by 23 experts from several European countries belonging to a variety of different sectors including industry, Small and Medium Enterprise (SMEs), research institutes and academia and having a professional background in telecommunication and Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility (CCAM) technologies. The derived results show that the "Basic PoDIUM features for enhanced system performance / capabilities" criterion is the most important one followed in turn by "CCAM Service Management Add-on features" and "Acceptance / Flexibility"; whilst "Business and Strategy" criterion has the lowest weight. Based on global priorities, the most weighted sub-criterion is that of "Trustworthiness of messages (authenticity and integrity)", followed by "Reliable Communications", "Security and Privacy", "RU detection and protection" and "Support heterogeneity of Road Users (RU) and communication channels".

1. Introduction

In this section, a brief description of the project is provided. The purpose and the intended audience of this deliverable is also included. The structure of the deliverable and its relation with other work packages/deliverables are also presented.

1.1. Project intro

In PoDIUM, using and enhancing the facilities of 3 well-equipped Living Labs in Germany, Italy and Spain we define a rich set of demanding CCAM use cases (UCs) to identify and assess all the connectivity and cooperation enablers and needs that will allow the proposed higher levels of automation. Building on the proposed UCs (urban and highway - incl. cross-border setups), which will be demonstrated and validated in real-life conditions, PoDIUM will tackle all the different requirements for availability and performance of connectivity as well as the different cooperation enablers per UC. The proposed UCs aim to advance a set of key technologies both in the physical and digital parts of the infrastructure. A multi-connectivity approach is followed to ensure the reliability, the availability and the redundancy of the Physical and Digital Infrastructure (PDI) system (i.e., ITS-G5, 5G, Long Term Evolution (LTE), 5G mmWave, 60GHz-WiFi, etc.). As part of the proposed PDI system, a distributed, interoperable and hybrid (Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) and cloud-based) data management environment will be implemented, which will include suitable advanced environment perception models and digital twins (DT) to facilitate seamless and efficient exchange of data (in low latency), thus enabling real-time analytics and opening up new business opportunities. Software integrity and data truthfulness of external data are important aspects that will be considered throughout the PDI to address existing gaps. New and standardised Cooperative Intelligent Transport System (C-ITS) messages will be integrated to support advanced functionalities, whereas new designs of Road-Side Units (RSUs) and On-Board Units (OBUs) will allow advanced environmental modelling and DTs based on locally generated data. Last but not least, a major focus will be laid on the integration of VRUs in the overall PDI. All those elements are integrated under the umbrella of the three-layered PoDIUM reference architecture, which is flexible and applicable in different road environments based on the available infrastructure equipment enabling different kinds of services.

1.2. Purpose of the deliverable

This deliverable presents the work undertaken in T6.1: Market research and actor-role analysis. The objectives of this deliverable are the following:

- Perform a market analysis by:
 - identifying the size and growth of relevant markets;
 - identifying the drivers, challenges and opportunities for each market;
 - deriving some regional insights;
 - identifying the main players in each market and competitive products (if possible).
- Define the ecosystem that will interact with the PoDIUM platform that is all the involved actors and roles, their relationships and revenue streams as well as potential service delivery options.
- Identify the factors that will affect the market adoption and evolution of PoDIUM solutions.

1.3. Intended audience

The dissemination level of D6.1 is 'public' (PU) and available to members of the consortium, the European Commission (EC) Services and experts outside the project. This deliverable can be used by both PoDIUM partners and other stakeholders involved in the CCAM industry since it provides useful guidelines for PoDIUM's platform exploitation. It can also serve as a baseline for both the business modelling activity and the technoeconomic analysis that will be performed in the same work package.

1.4. Structure of the deliverable and its relation with other work packages/deliverables

The deliverable has the following structure:

- In section 2, the results of the market analysis for the next-generation mobility market as well as for the markets related to the PoDIUM Key Exploitable Results (KERs) are presented.
- In section 3, the ecosystem around the PoDIUM platform is presented: the roles and the actors are defined along with their interactions. The main benefits of the PoDIUM platform for each of the actors are given.
- In section 4, the results of an online survey regarding the ranking of the factors that will affect the market adoption and evolution of PoDIUM solutions are discussed.
- In section 5, the concluding remarks are provided.

2. Market analysis

In this section, the market of next-generation mobility is discussed. First, an overall analysis of the market is performed, and then a market analysis for each of the PoDIUM Key Exploitable Results (KERs) is presented. For each component market, we perform an analysis of its i) dynamics, ii) regional characteristics, iii) segmentation and iv) competition.

2.1. Overall analysis of next generation mobility market

In this sub-section, the market of next generation mobility is presented and discussed. We divide this market into smart mobility, connected cars, autonomous vehicles (AVs) and ITS

2.1.1. Smart mobility market

According to Acumen Research and Consulting [3], the Global Smart Mobility Market is anticipated to reach \$91 billion by 2026, with a projected Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) 18.4% during the forecast period. As per a report by KBV Research [4], smart mobility involves diverse transportation modes to travel without personal vehicles, addressing issues like traffic congestion and pollution. Factors such as government support for smart cities and the rising demand for on-demand transportation drive market growth. Despite a decline during the COVID-19 pandemic, the market is expected to rebound. Ridesharing dominates the element segment, while traffic management leads in solutions.

Market dynamics:

- **Drivers:**
 - Government initiatives for smart cities and on-demand transportation drive market growth.
 - Technological advancements, including remote sensing and integrated communication systems, contribute to market growth.
 - Increasing demand for shared mobility, such as ride-sharing, is bolstering the smart mobility market.
- **Challenges:**
 - Low internet penetration; and
 - cybersecurity risks.

Regional market insights:

- North America is now leading the market, with the U.S. showing significant growth.
- Europe is expected to dominate the smart mobility market due to a growing population and the integration of advanced technologies.
- Asia Pacific is anticipated to have the fastest-growing market, driven by a high reliance on private vehicles and the potential for improvement in public transportation infrastructure.

Market segmentation:

- The market is segmented based on elements (bike commuting, car sharing, ride sharing), solutions (traffic management, parking management, mobility management), and technologies (3G & 4G, Wi-Fi, Global Positioning System (GPS), RFID, embedded system).
- Ridesharing and traffic management are prominent segments in elements and solutions, respectively.

- GPS and RFID are dominating the technology segment (Figure 1). The latter is used mainly for access-control to vehicles.

Figure 1: Smart Mobility Market Size by Technology (2020 – 2026) – Source: KBV Research

Competitive landscape:

- Cisco Systems and Toyota Motor Corporation are identified as forerunners in the market (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Smart Mobility Market Competition Analysis - Source: KBV Research

- Some key innovators of the market are: Siemens AG, TomTom N.V., Robert Bosch GmbH, Excelfore Corporation, and Ford Motor Company
- Partnerships, collaborations, acquisitions, and product launches are key strategies among market participants.
- Notable collaborations include Bosch with Microsoft, TomTom with Precisely, and Toyota with NTT.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, the Global Smart Mobility Market presents a dynamic landscape poised for significant expansion, as highlighted by forecasts from Acumen Research and Consulting and insights from KBV Research. With an anticipated reach of \$91 billion by 2026 and a projected CAGR of 18.4%, the sector showcases robust growth potential. Key drivers such as government support for smart cities and the rising demand for on-demand transportation fuel this growth, despite challenges like low internet

penetration and cybersecurity risks. Regional insights indicate North America's leadership, Europe's technological integration, and Asia Pacific's rapid advancement. The market segmentation underscores the dominance of ridesharing, traffic management, and RFID technology. Noteworthy players like Cisco Systems and Toyota Motor Corporation lead the competitive landscape, while innovators such as Siemens AG and Ford Motor Company drive advancements through strategic partnerships and product launches. As the industry continues to evolve, collaboration and innovation remain pivotal for shaping the future of smart mobility solutions globally.

2.1.2. Connected car market

As per a report by Allied Market Research [5], the global connected car market, valued at \$63.03 billion in 2019, is projected to reach \$225.16 billion by 2027, exhibiting a CAGR of 17.1%. As forecasted by “The Brainy Insights [6]”, the global connected vehicles (CVs) market is projected to reach USD 413.4 billion by 2032, growing at a CAGR of 18% from 2023 to 2032. According to Precedence Research [7], the global connected cars market size was estimated at USD 38.72 billion in 2023 and it is predicted to hit around USD 161.48 billion by 2033, growing at a CAGR of 15.40% between 2024 and 2033. Connected cars provide on-the-go connectivity, offering comfort, convenience, safety, and security through advanced network technology. The market is driven by increased consumer demand for connectivity, the growing tech-savvy population, and the need for constant connectivity. Various connectivity solutions, such as machine-to-machine (M2M) platforms, have been developed, enabling interconnectivity between connected cars and fueling market adoption globally. It should be highlighted that the connected cars market is in a transition phase, with a shift to 5G-enabled solutions. Advancements in diagnostic systems contribute to market growth.

Market dynamics

- **Drivers:**
 - Lack of road safety is a significant source of traffic accidents, prompting governments to prioritize traffic technology and accident reduction.
 - Surge in the need for constant connectivity.
 - Increase in the tech-savvy population.
- **Challenges:**
 - Improvement in global standards for vehicles.
 - The vulnerability to cyber-attacks is a major factor hindering market growth.
 - Lack of uninterrupted & seamless connectivity

Regional market insights:

- **North America:**
 - North America is the largest regional market with increased production and sales of vehicles supporting connected car services.
 - It is expected to witness the fastest growth, driven by investments in cybersecurity, the introduction of CAVs, and the adoption of advanced features like advanced driver assistance systems (ADAS).
 - Leading telecommunication companies, such as AT&T, contribute to the exponential growth of the connected cars network.
- **Asia Pacific:**
 - According to the Brainy Insights report, Asia Pacific dominates the CVs market with a 45% revenue share in 2022, driven by increasing demand for digital features in automobiles, particularly in China and India.

- The Asia Pacific connected cars market size was valued at USD 14.93 billion in 2023 and is expected to reach USD 63.37 billion by 2033, growing at a CAGR of 15.60% from 2024 to 2033 (Figure 3).

Figure 3 Asia Pacific Connected Car market size

- **Europe:**
 - The Europe-connected cars market revenue by the end of 2021 was US\$ 10.2 Billion. The Europe-connected cars market is expected to reach US\$ 49.7 Billion by 2032, as it is estimated to grow at a CAGR of 15.6% from 2022 to 2032.
 - EU is establishing different vehicle-related rules and regulations, which is a welcome step for connected car manufacturers and dealers.
 - The availability of modern telecommunications and road infrastructure will also continue to stimulate the European automobile market.
 - Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs) are focusing on strengthening the market.

Market segmentation:

- Segments include technology (3G, 4G/LTE, 5G), connectivity solutions (integrated, embedded, tethered), services (driver assistance, safety, entertainment, well-being, vehicle management, mobility management), and end use (OEM, aftermarket).
- 5G technology is projected as the most lucrative segment, with embedded connectivity being the dominant solution.
- Driver assistance is projected as the most lucrative segment.

Competitive landscape: Major players in the market include Airbiquity Inc., CloudMade, Continental AG, Qualcomm Technologies, Inc., Robert Bosch GmbH, Tesla, AT&T, Audi AG, BMW Group, Delphi Technologies PLC, Harman International Industries, Inc., Infineon Technologies AG, NXP Semiconductors N.V., Toyota Motor Corporation, Valeo, ZF Friedrichshafen AG, BorgWarner.

Recent developments:

- In April 2022, Obigo Inc. and Korea Electric Technology Institute collaborated on 5G-NR-V2X technologies for Connected and Autonomous Vehicles (CAVs).
- In January 2022, Aptiv PLC announced a next-gen ADAS for driverless and electrified vehicles.
- In November 2021, Continental introduced a technology solution for highly automated driving with a cutting-edge software solution called Next Generation Driving Planner
- In January 2020, Continental AG launched an online portal for digitally CV architectures.
- In January 2020, LUXOFT partnered with Microsoft to enhance CV solutions.
- In January 2020, Qualcomm introduced a car-to-cloud service for future-proofing vehicles.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, the connected car market is poised for remarkable growth, as evidenced by various forecasts and market analyses. With projections indicating substantial expansion in revenue and adoption rates, the industry stands at the forefront of technological advancement and innovation. The surge in demand for constant connectivity, coupled with advancements in diagnostic systems and the transition to 5G-enabled solutions, underpins the market's evolution. However, challenges such as cybersecurity vulnerabilities and the high maintenance costs of advanced systems necessitate continued vigilance and innovation. Regional insights highlight diverse opportunities and trends, with North America, Asia Pacific, and Europe emerging as key hubs of growth and development. As major players and stakeholders invest in cutting-edge technologies and collaborative initiatives, the connected car market is positioned to redefine mobility, safety, and convenience in the automotive industry. Recent developments underscore the industry's dynamism and the commitment to driving forward-looking solutions that anticipate and address evolving consumer needs and regulatory requirements. As the market continues to evolve, strategic partnerships, regulatory frameworks, and technological advancements will play pivotal roles in shaping its trajectory and unlocking new possibilities for CVs worldwide.

2.1.3. Autonomous vehicles market

As stated in a report published by Straits Research [9], the global AV market is poised for significant growth, with a projected value of USD 51.958 billion by 2031, growing at a CAGR of 12.1% during the forecast period from 2023 to 2031. Key factors contributing to this growth include the numerous advantages offered by AVs, increased government support, and the development of adaptive technologies.

In addition to the advantages for consumers, Autonomous Driving (AD) has the potential to create added value for the automotive industry. Currently, most vehicles are equipped with basic ADAS features, but significant progress in AD capabilities is on the horizon. Eventually, automobiles will attain Level 4 (L4), allowing for driverless control under specific conditions. A 2021 McKinsey consumer survey indicates that consumers desire access to AD features and are willing to invest in them. Considering the consumer interest in AD features and the commercial solutions presently available, McKinsey's analysis suggests that the combined market for ADAS and AD in the passenger car segment could reach a substantial \$300 billion to \$400 billion by 2035 (Figure 4).

Figure 4 Advanced driver-assistance systems and autonomous-driving systems revenues (source: McKinsey [8])

Market dynamics:

- **Drivers:**
 - **Benefits offered:** AVs provide various benefits such as reduced road-crash risk, decreased traffic congestion, enhanced safety, lower fuel consumption, efficient parking, and improved mobility for disabled individuals. These advantages drive the growth of the market.
 - **Government support:** Governments globally are making regulatory changes to encourage the development of AVs. Acts like the Motor Vehicles (Amendment) Act 2019 in India and initiatives by the United States Department of Transportation support the safe development, testing, and adoption of automated vehicle technologies.
- **Challenges:**
 - **Lack of infrastructure in developing nations:** Emerging countries lack the necessary infrastructure, including well-maintained roads, GPS connectivity, and efficient communication networks, to accommodate self-driving cars. Poor infrastructure and driving discipline present obstacles for AVs in these regions.

Regional market insights:

- **Europe:** Holds the largest market share due to government support and increasing demand for AVs. Significant OEMs in Germany, such as BMW, Volkswagen AG, and Tesla Inc., contribute to the region's market dominance.
- **North America:** Has the second-largest market share, driven by a growing demand for technologically advanced products, favourable government policies, and the presence of industry leaders like Apple, Google, and Mercedes-Benz.
- **Asia Pacific:** Experiences the fastest growth, with Chinese and Japanese efforts in self-driving technology development. Rising consumer demand, safety regulations, and increasing disposable income contribute to the region's market expansion.
- **Latin America and Middle East & Africa (LAMEA):** Hold the least share in the global market. Efforts like the Mobility Center for Africa aim to promote connected, autonomous, shared, and electric vehicles in South Africa.

Market segmentation:

- **Level of Automation:** Level 2 and Level 3 automation, representing semi-autonomous vehicles, are expected to grow the fastest. Level 2 provides steering and acceleration/deceleration controls, while Level 3 includes "environmental detection" and autonomous decision-making.
- **Components:** Software dominates the market, with self-driving cars utilizing artificial intelligence for environmental comprehension and decision-making.
- **Application:** The commercial segment, including ride-sharing and robotic taxis, is expected to grow the fastest. Businesses invest in AVs for ride-sharing, ride-hailing, and car-sharing, contributing to improved fleet management.

Competitive landscape: The market is driven by General Motors, Google, Volkswagen, Ford Motor Company, BMW, Baidu, Tesla, Toyota, Audi, Jaguar etc.

Recent developments:

- In April 2022, Toyota subsidiary Woven Planet adopted a camera-only approach for its self-driving project, similar to Tesla, to enhance cost-effectiveness and self-driving capabilities.
- In August 2022, BMW opened a new autonomous car testing center in the Czech Republic, focusing on evaluating vehicle performance in various scenarios.

Conclusion:

The future of AVs appears promising, with significant growth anticipated in the global market. The projected value of nearly USD 52 billion by 2031 reflects the increasing demand for autonomous driving technology. Advantages such as enhanced safety, reduced congestion, and improved mobility, coupled with government support and technological advancements, drive this growth trajectory. Despite challenges like infrastructure limitations in emerging economies, market dynamics indicate a robust momentum, particularly in regions like Europe, North America, and the Asia Pacific. With key players investing in innovative solutions and recent developments such as Toyota's camera-only approach and BMW's testing center, the landscape of AVs continues to evolve, offering immense opportunities for industry stakeholders and consumers alike. As the market expands and technologies mature, AVs are poised to revolutionize transportation systems worldwide, heralding a new era of mobility and efficiency.

2.1.4. Intelligent transportation system market

The ITS) market, valued at \$25 billion in 2022, is projected to reach \$55.54 billion by 2031, growing at a CAGR of 7.8% [10]. Verified Market Research [11] reports that the global ITS market size was valued at USD 52.59 Billion in 2021 and is projected to reach USD 96.68 Billion by 2030, with a CAGR of 6.7% from 2022 to 2030. As per a report by Allied Market Research [12], the global ITS market is experiencing significant growth, with a valuation of \$48.36 billion in 2022, projected to reach \$98.02 billion by 2032, at a CAGR of 7.5%. Reportlinker.com [13] forecasted that the global ITS market is anticipated to exceed USD 51.2 billion by 2030, experiencing a CAGR of 14.9% from USD 15.9 billion in 2020. The European Union has defined ITS as systems using technology to manage road transport infrastructure, vehicles, users, traffic, mobility, and interfaces with other transportation modes. ITS leverages information and communication technologies (ICT) to enhance transportation safety, efficiency, and management. The ITS market includes various systems such as Commercial Vehicle Operation, Advanced Traffic Management System, and applications like Automotive Telematics, Collision Avoidance. Deployment of ITS helps provide real-time traffic statistics, aiding in resolving increased traffic congestion. Intelligent signals control and gather information from sensors, including vehicle speed, pre-emption alarms, and traffic signals, contributing to efficient traffic management.

Market dynamics:

- **Drivers:**
 - **Growing need for road safety:**
 1. Lack of road safety is a significant source of traffic accidents, prompting governments to prioritize traffic technology and accident reduction.
 2. Various projects aim to integrate advanced traffic control technologies to improve road safety, increasing demand for Vehicle-to-Vehicle (V2V) and Vehicle-to-Infrastructure (V2I) known as Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) communication.
 - **Development of smart and connected vehicular platforms:**
 1. The CCAM concept is transforming the automotive industry, promoting effective V2X communication.
 2. The concept is expected to enhance road safety, traffic efficiency, and driving comfort, creating opportunities for ITS growth.
 - **Rapid urbanization:** The growth of the market is driven by rapid urbanization and recent technological advancements.

- **Collaborative efforts:** Collaborative efforts for developing efficient transportation networks between countries, irrespective of barriers, contribute to market growth.
- **Congestion in cities:** ITS provides real-time traffic statistics, aiding in resolving traffic congestion. It assists drivers in identifying quicker and traffic-free routes.
- **Challenges:** High installation costs and the need for a centralized traffic management center (TMC), along with various devices, pose challenges. Devices like CCTV cameras, microwave detectors, highway advisory radios, dynamic message signs, and advanced traveler information systems are required, limiting widespread adoption.
- **Opportunities:** Despite challenges, the growth of connected and autonomous driving cars, along with advancements in high-speed internet and communication technologies, provides lucrative opportunities.

Regional market insights:

- **North America:**
 - Largest market shareholder with a 3% estimated CAGR over the forecast period.
 - Quick adoption of intelligent transportation technologies due to government focus on strengthening transportation infrastructure.
- **Asia Pacific:**
 - Technological advancements and the continued expansion of transportation networks are likely to boost the growth of the Asia Pacific ITS market.
 - The economic benefits of ITS deployment are particularly noticeable in nations such as China, India, and Japan.
- **Europe:**
 - Anticipated CAGR of 7.3% over the forecast period.
 - European Commission and member states developing a standardized approach for integrating ITS into current infrastructure to enhance transportation efficiency.

Market segmentation:

- **Applications:** Traffic Management segment holds the highest market share, expected to exhibit a 5.7% CAGR. According to ReportLinker.com report, automotive telematics is anticipated to grow with the highest CAGR during 2020-30, driven by rising demand for driver assistance systems and automatic driving systems.
- **End users:** Roadways is projected as the most lucrative segment.

Competitive landscape: Key players include Alstom SA, Garmin Ltd., Teledyne FLIR LLC, Hitachi, DENSO, Siemens, Thales Group, Kapsch TrafficCom, SWARCO, Addco, Agero, EFKON, Garmin, and Xerox Corporation, TomTom International B.V., Cubic Corporation, Garmin Ltd., Q-Free ASA, EFKON GmbH, FLIR Systems, Inc., and Denso Corporation, NEC Corporation, Cubic Transportation Systems, Inc, Navico, Group.

Recent developments:

- In November 2023: Acquisition of HMM, a manufacturer of the MIREL train protection system for Slovakia, Czech Republic, Hungary, and Poland, enhancing Siemens Mobility's rail infrastructure portfolio.

- In October 2023: Partnership between Alstom SA & FLXO Robotics to develop technology for reducing wildlife collision accidents using advanced image analytics and AI algorithms.
- In August 2023, NEC Corporation & Uttar Pradesh State Road Transport Corporation inked a contract for the Vehicle Location Tracking-Passenger Information System (VLT-PSIS) project in India, addressing safety concerns and improving passengers' travel experiences.
- In May 2023, Kenya Urban Roads Authority (KURA) opened a tender for the Nairobi Intelligent Transport System (ITS) phase one project worth \$8.4 billion.
- In April 2023, India and Russia to implement sophisticated transport and logistics, fostering cooperation in road transportation, logistics, ITS, and green mobility.
- In August 2021, Siemens Mobility signed a contract to deliver a comprehensive rail system, featuring the first-ever high-speed line, transforming transportation in Egypt.
- In August 2021, agreement for the sale of Thales Group's Ground Transportation System segment to Hitachi Rail, strengthening Hitachi's mobility offerings and presence in rail signaling.
- In June 2021, Kapsch TrafficCom secured a project to implement a new toll collection system for the Louisiana Highway for the Louisiana Department of Transportation and Development.
- In January 2019, Siemens signed a four-year contract with The Department for Infrastructure in Northern Ireland for the maintenance and development of existing traffic management systems.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, the ITS market is poised for substantial growth driven by factors such as the pressing need for road safety, the emergence of smart and connected vehicular platforms, rapid urbanization, and collaborative efforts to enhance transportation networks globally. Despite facing challenges like high installation costs and the requirement for centralized TMCs, the market is buoyed by opportunities presented by the rise of connected and autonomous driving cars and advancements in communication technologies. With significant developments and partnerships underway across various regions, including acquisitions, partnerships, and infrastructure projects, the ITS market is on track to revolutionize transportation efficiency, safety, and management. As key players continue to innovate and collaborate, the ITS landscape is expected to evolve dynamically, shaping the future of transportation worldwide.

2.2. Market analysis of PoDIUM KERs

PoDIUM has identified eight KERs, i.e., specific areas that it aims to have a significant impact on. In this clause, we perform an analysis of each corresponding market, and we provide the main differentiating factors of PoDIUM.

2.2.1. CAVs and VRUs market

According to a report published by Maximize Market Research [1], the CAVs Market, valued at USD 106.66 billion in 2022, is projected to witness rapid growth, reaching nearly USD 1129.97 billion by 2029, at a remarkable CAGR of 40.1% from 2023 to 2029. The advancements in AI, connectivity and sensor capabilities is anticipated to be the primary driver for this growth. This market represents the convergence of cutting-edge technologies, including connectivity, automation, and artificial intelligence, shaping the future of transportation towards safer, more efficient, and sustainable mobility. CAVs, as intelligent vehicles with self-driving capabilities, aim to increase the safety of

passengers and RU and at the same time contribute to reducing traffic accidents, road congestion, environmental pollution levels, etc.

Within the vehicular traffic ecosystem, the Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs) include pedestrians, cyclists, and motorcyclists, among others. To the best of our knowledge, this is a niche market with limited commercial interest, at least for now. PoDIUM is focusing mainly on the integration of VRUs with the help of enhanced perception modules and their direct connection to the system.

Market dynamics:

- **Drivers:**
 - **Improved road safety:** AVs are expected to significantly reduce accidents caused by human error, contributing to enhanced road safety.
 - **Environmental sustainability:** The focus on environmental sustainability and combating climate change is driving the adoption of connected and autonomous electric vehicles, contributing to reduced carbon emissions.
 - **Efficiency and optimization:** CAVs optimize traffic flow, reduce congestion, and enhance transportation efficiency. Continuous advancements in sensor technology, AI, and data processing propel the development of AVs.
 - **Rise of mobility services:** Innovations in mobility services such as ride-sharing and Mobility-as-a-Service (MaaS) platforms have increased the demand for connected and AVs.
 - **Government support:** Governments worldwide actively support CAV development and adoption through regulation and financial incentives.
 - **EU and national initiatives:** Supportive regulatory frameworks and government initiatives, along with the extensive funding of related research by EC, are promoting connected and automated mobility and hence provide a conducive environment for market growth.
 - **Secure local access to vehicle data:** The recent security-related developments on data management, legal framework construction through data act, SVI, etc. are facilitating the adoption of CAVs.
 - **Cooperative mobility:** Cooperative mobility [2] involving millions of connected cars sharing data messages about road and traffic conditions is expected to improve coordination, anticipate hazards, and enhance traffic flow.
- **Challenges:**
 - **Safety concerns:** Ensuring the safety and reliability of fully AVs with fail-safe systems remains a complex and expensive challenge for manufacturers and regulators.
 - **Infrastructure availability and upgrades:** The deployment of CAVs relies on advanced infrastructure, including high-quality road networks, smart traffic signals, and communication systems, necessitating costly upgrades.
 - **Interoperability issues:** the existence of different technologies, like Cooperative Vehicle-to-Everything (C-V2X) and Dedicated Short-Range Communications (DSRC, a.k.a. ITS-G5) introduces the risk of deployed infrastructure becoming obsolete; similar risks come from non-standardized supplier equipment.
 - **Regulatory fragmentation:** Lack of standardized regulations for Connected and Autonomous Mobility Vehicles (CAMVs) across different regions and countries poses a challenge to widespread adoption.

- **Data security:** CVs are susceptible to cybersecurity threats, including hacking and data breaches, highlighting the importance of ensuring the security and privacy of data transmitted and received by CAMVs.
- **Public perception:** Convincing the general public about CAMV safety and reliability is a challenge, and overcoming skepticism and fear of autonomous technology is crucial for widespread acceptance.
- **Opportunities:**
 - **Data monetization:** The vast amounts of data generated by CAMVs offer opportunities for data-driven services and insights, leading to potential data monetization.
 - **New business models:** Despite challenges, the market offers opportunities for new business models, data monetization, and improved user experience, contributing to increased innovation.

Regional market insights:

- **North America:** Leading the CAMV market, North America benefits from a strong automotive industry and a vibrant technology ecosystem. Government support and permissive regulations encourage extensive trials and pilot programs by companies like Waymo, Tesla, and GM's Cruise.
- **Europe:** Strong government support and initiatives in countries like Germany, the UK, and Sweden, coupled with a robust automotive industry, drive CAMV development. Urbanization and sustainable transportation needs propel CAMVs in crowded cities like London, Paris, and Berlin.
- **Asia-Pacific:** Fast-growing urban centers in Asia-Pacific, especially China and Singapore, are driving demand for smart and efficient mobility solutions. Heavy investments in AI and AV technologies contribute to market growth.

The forecasted shared micro-mobility market in the different regions is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: The shared micro-mobility market in China, Europe, and the US in 2029, (in Billion)

Market segmentation:

- **Vehicle Level of Automation:** Passenger vehicles dominate the CAV market (Figure 6), driven by enhanced safety, convenience, and improved mobility solutions. Commercial vehicles, including autonomous delivery vehicles and trucks, show potential for revolutionizing logistics and transportation.

Figure 6: Mobility split by mode of transportation, worldwide, 2022, (%)

Competitive landscape: Key players in the CAV market include AB Volvo, Amazon Web Services, Inc., Aptiv, ARTHUR D. LITTLE, AVL, BMW AG, Daimler AG, Dassault Systèmes, Ford Motor Company, FutureBridge, General Motors, Honda, Motor Co., Ltd., Hyundai Motor Company, Infineon Technologies AG, Nissan Motors Co., Ltd., Renault Group, SAE International, Segula Technologies, Swiss Re, Tesla, Inc., Toyota Motor Corporation, UITP Advanced Public Transport, Volkswagen AG, WirelessCar, WSP, ZF, Lohr, Continental, Local Motors, Easymile, Nutonomy, 2getthere, Mobileye. This provides huge opportunities to serve many end-uses & customers and expand the CAMV Market.

It is thus evident that the CAV market promises exponential growth and innovation, with transformative effects on transportation and mobility. It brings together technologies like connectivity, automation, and artificial intelligence, presenting opportunities for increased safety, efficiency, and environmental sustainability. Integrating CAMVs into urban planning and infrastructure is seen as a key enabler for efficient traffic management, optimized routing, and seamless communication between vehicles and transportation systems. The market is expected to shape the future of transportation positively.

Comparison between the PoDIUM approach and the competition

PoDIUM involves mainly passenger cars. Each PoDIUM CAV is enhanced with certain developments that will help us reach higher levels of automation and increased safety. The main differentiating factors of PoDIUM CAVs are:

- Sharing the origin and destination of their current trip with PoDIUM services, for specific functionalities related to traffic optimization in general and for Emergency Vehicles (EV).
- Receive and execute cooperative manoeuvres recommendations, as well as optimal route recommendations in the format of ETSI Manoeuvre Coordination Message (MCM) with suitable extensions.
- Receive and react to collision risk alerts in the form of ETSI Decentralized Environmental Notification Message (DENM).
- Exchange bilaterally ETSI Cooperative Perception Messages (CPM) messages with PoDIUM services that, for some innovative functionalities, shall require extensions to include information about:

- o Uncertainties about the RUs' states.
- o Prediction of future trajectories of RUs.
- o Sensor data.
- Support remote attestation through the *Software Integrity* service, verifying the integrity of the software in the vehicle.

Finally, the PoDIUM shuttle CAVs, also support:

- Specific tele-supervision commands.
- Real Time Kinematic (RTK) corrections.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, the CAVs market stands at the forefront of technological innovation, poised for exponential growth and transformative impact on transportation and mobility. With a projected CAGR of 40.1% from 2023 to 2029, this market converges cutting-edge technologies such as AI, connectivity, and automation to revolutionize safety, efficiency, and environmental sustainability in transportation. Despite facing challenges like safety concerns and regulatory fragmentation, CAVs offer immense opportunities for data monetization, new business models, and enhanced user experiences. As regions worldwide invest in smart mobility solutions and companies race to innovate, the CAV market is set to shape the future of transportation positively, paving the way for safer, more efficient, and sustainable mobility ecosystems globally.

2.2.2. Multi-connectivity and short-range communications market

V2V communications [14]-[17] refers to the technology used in automobiles for short-range communications. The demand for seamless and reliable communication solutions is escalating as the automotive industry inches towards autonomous and CVs.

On the other hand, multi-path connectivity for CCAM services is a niche market, which is difficult to quantify and hence no market data are available. As the automotive industry increasingly focuses on enhancing the reliability and efficiency of communication systems for CAVs, the demand for multipath solutions is gaining traction. The integration of technologies that enable simultaneous communication over multiple paths is becoming a key enabler for safer and more robust CCAM (Cooperative Connected and Automated Mobility) systems.

Notice that here we focus on multi-path connectivity for CCAM which we distinguish from other multi-connectivity approaches like Apple's proprietary MPTCP solution utilized in SIRI¹ or other multi-technology connectivity solutions used for management of critical infrastructures such as aviation systems².

The market is poised for substantial expansion in the coming years. According to industry analysts [15], the global V2V communication market size will grow from \$22 billion in 2023 to \$24.82 billion in 2024 at a CAGR of 12.8%. The V2V communication market size is expected to grow to 40.28 billion in 2028 at a CAGR of 12.9%.

¹ <https://support.apple.com/en-us/101905#>

² <https://www.airport-suppliers.com/supplier/damm/>

The increasing adoption of CAVs, coupled with advancements in communication protocols, is anticipated to be the primary driver for this growth. Multi-connectivity enabling enhanced reliability and lower latency is expected to contribute to the uptake of CCAM.

Market dynamics

- **Drivers**

- **Rising adoption of CAVs:** The ongoing proliferation of CAVs is a key driver, necessitating robust communication infrastructure for safe and efficient CCAM services and operations.
- **EU and national initiatives:** Supportive regulatory frameworks and government initiatives, along with the extensive funding of related research by EC, are promoting connected and automated mobility and hence provide a conducive environment for market growth.
- **Availability of standardized V2V technological advancements:** Continuous advancements in communication technologies, such as the 5G support of i) short-range communications (see Proximity Services-ProSe) and ii) multi-connectivity (see Access Traffic Steering, Switching and Splitting- ATSSS), are enhancing the reliability and speed of short-range communications, fostering market growth. The existence of standardized solutions ensures interoperability and hence broader adoption of V2V communications by the market.

- **Challenges**

- **Privacy & security concerns:** The V2V communication paradigm requires that each vehicle trusts for its interactions a vast number of other entities/vehicles that it may encounter along its path. The lack of any centralized infrastructure to act as the trusted authority for authentication and authorization raises concerns about privacy preservation and cybersecurity, posing a challenge to the widespread adoption of short-range communication solutions.
- **Infrastructure availability:** The successful implementation of CCAM relies heavily on the readiness of the existing infrastructure. Whereas equipping each vehicle with certain communication technologies is quite easy, the deployment of roadside infrastructure supporting short range communications is a costly operation. This could result in extended regions with inadequate infrastructure, and the growth of the market may be hindered.
- **Alternative technologies and interoperability issues:** The existence of 2 alternative technologies, namely C-V2x and Dedicated Short-Range Communications (DSRC, a.k.a. ITS-G5) introduces the risk of deployed infrastructure becoming obsolete. Besides, the lack of interoperability among the different available communication solutions may impede seamless integration into the existing automotive ecosystem.

Competitive landscape

- **DSRC /ITS-G5:** Dedicated Short-Range Communications is a technology, providing low-latency communication for V2V and V2I applications. Its reliability and maturity make it a preferred choice in some regions. DSRC has been widely used because of its unique properties such as low latency and high reliability. The United States Federal Communications Commission (FCC) allocated 75 MHz of spectrum in the 5.9 GHz band to be employed for vehicle to vehicle and vehicle to infrastructure communication, whereas, the European Telecommunications

Standards Institute (ETSI) allocated 30 MHz of spectrum in the 5.9 GHz band. The DSRC technology market is projected to grow from USD 2.5 billion in 2022 to USD 9.3 billion by 2032, at a CAGR of 13.9% [16].

- **C-V2X (Cellular Vehicle-to-Everything):** Leveraging cellular networks, C-V2X offers both direct communication and network-based communication, providing enhanced flexibility and scalability. Both LTE and 5G versions exist, but the latter is gaining traction with the ongoing global rollout of 5G cellular networks. C-V2X Technology Market Cap Hit USD 1039.4 Million. C-V2X Technology Market Cap Expected to Reach USD 12130 Million in Upcoming Years, growing at a CAGR of 50.6% [17].

Comparison between the PoDIUM approach and the competition

All available technologies are as generally considered adequate for the basic CCAM requirements. Especially, the recent standardization of proximity services over 5G to support V2V direct communications is an important milestone that could affect the market development in the years to come.

With the ongoing development of novel, more demanding CCAM services towards DTs and cooperative manoeuvres a re-evaluation of the situation is needed. An overview of the main characteristics of each competitive technology is provided below:

- **Latency & throughput:** DSRC, being a dedicated short-range technology, often boasts lower latency compared to C-V2X, which relies on cellular networks. However, C-V2X offers higher data transfer rates under good coverage conditions, mainly due to its increased available bandwidth, enabling more data-intensive applications.
- **Scalability:** C-V2X has the advantage of leveraging existing cellular infrastructure, making it more scalable overall. DSRC, on the other hand, requires additional infrastructure investments for widespread implementation, and there is no consensus on who would be undertaking the task of installation and maintenance of this infrastructure.

The PoDIUM approach tries to bring together the best of both worlds through i) multi-connectivity and ii) by exploring the option of using 60GHz WiFi. This frequency band is part of the millimeter-wave spectrum and is often associated with the IEEE 802.11ad and IEEE 802.11ay standards for Wi-Fi communication.

The 60GHz frequency band offers a high frequency and wide bandwidth, providing the potential for high data transfer rates, which could serve ideally CCAM applications that require instantaneous and reliable data exchange, such as V2V and V2I communications. Note that this is a short-range communication technology and the 60GHz frequency band faces challenges related to signal propagation, as signals in this range are more susceptible to obstacles like walls and atmospheric absorption.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the market for short-range communications for CCAM is dynamic, with a positive growth trajectory. The choice between DSRC and C-V2X involves a trade-off between latency, scalability, and infrastructure requirements, and this dynamic landscape will continue to evolve as technology advances and regulatory frameworks mature. Most of the PoDIUM developments are agnostic to the

communication technology used and through multi-connectivity, we pursue the creation of a hybrid approach.

2.2.3. Digital twins market

To the best of our knowledge, there is no CCAM DT product in the market, and hence we perform an analysis of the overall DT market. The (DT) market is a rapidly expanding sector with broad applications across various industries, reflecting its capacity to integrate the physical and virtual environments. The market was valued at around USD 11.13 billion in 2022 and it is anticipated to grow significantly, with estimates suggesting a CAGR between 37.5% to 61.3% from 2023 to 2030, depending on the source. This growth is propelled by several core technologies, such as the Internet of Things (IoT), artificial intelligence, Extended Reality (XR), and cloud computing [18]-[20].

In terms of sector-specific analysis, the manufacturing, automotive, aviation, energy, utilities, healthcare, logistics, and retail industries have adopted DTs to enhance productivity and efficiency. The manufacturing sector along with energy and power, aerospace, oil and gas, and automobile industries, are key segments where DTs are heavily utilized [21]-[22].

Expanding on the market analysis of DTs, it is evident that this technology is not just an isolated tool but an ecosystem that interacts with various sectors and technologies, as shown below.

- **Manufacturing:** In manufacturing, DTs are used for monitoring equipment, optimizing production processes, and simulating factories for better resource management. The real-time data provided by DTs helps in predictive maintenance, thus reducing downtime and extending the life of machinery. The integration of IoT with DTs allows for a more interconnected and intelligent manufacturing environment, leading to the rise of smart factories.
- **Automotive:** The automotive industry benefits from DTs in several ways, from the design and engineering of vehicles to the maintenance and prediction of vehicle performance under various conditions. DTs enable manufacturers to test and optimize vehicle performance without physical prototypes, saving both time and costs.
- **Aerospace:** The application of DTs in aerospace is quite extensive. They are used in the design and testing of aircraft, monitoring aircraft health, and managing maintenance schedules. The ability to track real-time data and simulate conditions leads to improved safety and efficiency in aircraft operations.
- **Energy and Utilities:** DTs are transforming the energy sector by optimizing the performance of renewable energy sources and predicting maintenance for utility infrastructure. In power plants, DTs simulate operations to maximize efficiency and anticipate potential failures before they occur.
- **Healthcare:** In healthcare, DTs can revolutionize patient care by providing personalized health models for predictive diagnostics and treatment plans. Hospitals are also using DTs to manage their facilities more effectively, from optimizing patient flow to monitoring equipment.
- **Oil and Gas:** The oil and gas sector uses DTs to simulate drilling operations, predict equipment failures, and optimize the performance of the extraction process. This not only enhances safety by anticipating potential hazards but also maximizes yield and efficiency.
- **Retail and Logistics:** Retailers are using DTs to manage inventory and optimize supply chains. In logistics, DTs of warehouses and distribution networks help improve delivery times and reducing costs by simulating and optimizing routes and logistics operations.

- **Real Estate and Urban Planning:** DTs are employed in building and city planning to simulate environments, manage facilities, and optimize energy consumption. They help in creating more sustainable and efficient living and working spaces by analyzing data on traffic patterns, utility usage, and human behavior.

The cross-sectoral impact of DTs is also significant. For example, the convergence of DTs with blockchain technology can offer a new level of security and trust in data management. The combination with big data analytics, 5G, and machine learning paves the way for autonomous systems and smarter decision-making processes.

Market dynamics

- **Drivers**
 - The healthcare industry shows a growing demand for DTs, with a keen focus on predictive maintenance. This technology plays a crucial role in product design and development, especially in the aerospace sector, which is expected to dominate the market for DT applications in the forecast period [23]-[24].
 - DT technology is recognized for its unique ability to provide a digital replica or model of any physical object, facilitating an automatic bidirectional exchange of data between the digital and physical entities in real-time. Such capabilities have made it an essential component in vehicle engineering, design modifications, and maintenance within the automotive and aerospace sectors. Notably, in aerospace, it assists in weight monitoring, aircraft tracking, precise weather forecasting, and identifying vehicle flaws [25]-**Error! Reference source not found.**
 - The increasing digitalization and integration with IoT are current trends that deliver DT usage to naturally increase.
 - The transversality of DTs is a key factor in the market growth since DTs can be applied to:
 - End use: Automotive, Agriculture, Manufacturing
 - Solutions: Component, System, product
 - Applications: Business, Predictive maintenance
 - Industry: Healthcare, Transportation, Energy.
- **Challenges**
 - **Required Infrastructure.** The advanced digital infrastructure that is required to run a DT is one of the highest challenges. It requires an environment based on models. This is complex since all objects have to be modelled in their complexity, and making them interoperable is complex. Organizations must be prepared to adopt this modelling.
 - **Maintenance.** After the creation of a DT, information maintenance is necessary. Physical objects have a lifecycle and would deviate for sure from their digital counterparts for different reasons such as age and operating conditions. If the DT is not a synchronized representation of the physical object, its purpose vanishes.
It is difficult to maintain a digital asset. Many DT efforts fail because the digital assets don't receive the same maintenance effort as the physical ones. The DT requires consistent upkeep, significant observation, and time to document all real-time changes. If done properly, the DT should provide insight into the effects of operating conditions before the physical twin experiences them.
 - **Privacy and security concerns.** The combination of information from several IoT sensors and other digital technologies to recreate a digital replica builds an increasing danger of

security, since anonymous individuals can acquire information about the DT's internals and details with illegitimate intentions.

Regional market insights

Regionally, the North American DT market had a value of approximately USD 4 billion in 2022, but the Asia-Pacific market is predicted to witness substantial growth, with a projected CAGR of over 41%. This indicates a worldwide acceptance and integration of DT technologies, fostering digitalization across industries [27].

From a geographical perspective, the expansion of DTs is global. In Europe, there is significant growth in the adoption of DTs, especially in countries with strong manufacturing and automotive sectors. The European market is also driven by the increasing focus on Industry 4.0 and the integration of DTs with existing industrial infrastructure.

The varied applications and technological integrations of DTs demonstrate their pivotal role in the modern digital landscape, making them an essential tool for various sectors seeking efficiency, productivity, and innovation.

Competitive landscape

- Siemens has versions of DTs for product design, production lines, and operations performance [28]. The product is called NX.
- Maximo is the product name of IBM, again, oriented to industry, manufacturing and healthcare.
- Oracle Internet of Things Cloud Service is an oracle product oriented to predictive maintenance in industry and business

These products are usually a compound of DT plus all models, assistants, simulators and other components that constitute most of the product, in industry applications for production lines.

At the moment, apparently there is not a commercial solution for road and transportation DTs. Initiatives have been found in research on this topic, coming from Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) for road planning. No products are present also for people's road selection habits, and planning or CCAM applications. So, according to the consortium knowledge, there are currently no commercially available competitors in the CCAM sector.

Comparison between the PoDIUM approach and the competition

Mainly one of the limitations of existing DT solutions are that they are based on a manufacturing process that has to be optimized through an iterative process of modelling, simulation, learning, etc. In PODIUM, the focus is mainly on the safety and rising of real-time conditions or warnings; the CCAM cannot be modelled as a production process. The advantages of the PoDIUM approach are:

- CCAM-oriented data. It is strictly provided with real-time data coming from the roads/streets.
- The concentration of road data in a single place enriches the situational awareness of actors such as CAVs and the services that produce output consumed by CAVs.
- Safety-critical data: rapidly changing but also valid for coarse/statistical analysis. As a consequence of situational awareness, road safety is increased, which adds much value to PODIUM CCAM services that use DTs.

- Geo-localized: data can scale since the DT’s domain might be confined geographically to a crosspoint/tunnel in the case of three of PODIUM UCs; this makes management easier since all data producers are interested in uploading their data to receive the service’s output. Also, vehicles as data producers have a short life in the system.
- The data truthfulness and trustworthiness of the information that feeds the DT is unique given the criticality of the information that enhances safety.

Currently, CCAM DTs are in a premature phase since the idea of using DTs into the CCAM environment is innovative. As far as the author's knowledge, other EU projects, such as 5GMETA [29], are also bringing DT definitions into the CCAM environment. Some comparisons might be made between 5GMETA and PODIUM’s DTs (Table 1).

Table 1 Comparison between 5GMETA and PODIUM’s digital twins solutions

	PODIUM-DT	5GMETA-DT
Year of implementation	2024	2021
Geographical coverage scale	Localized: Crosspoints, tunnels, city, crossborder	Specific for UCs
API types	proprietary	Proprietary, REST
External apps allowed	no	yes
Information contained is tagged with truth level (truthfulness)	yes	no
CAVs are trust sources of data (with attestation and TPM obus)	yes	no
Runs on MEC-only	MEC-cloud	MEC
Oriented to third parties participation	No	Yes

Conclusion:

The DT market is expected to experience significant growth with a CAGR of 37.5% to 61.3% from 2023 to 2030, driven by technologies like IoT, AI, XR, and cloud computing. Although currently no CCAM DT commercial solution exists, it is expected that enhanced connected mobility will enable more integrated and dynamic interactions between the physical and digital infrastructure.

2.2.4. Automated traffic management centres Market

Automated Traffic Management Centers (ATMCs) provide traffic solutions via a cloud platform, utilizing technology and data to monitor and optimize traffic and transportation systems. It offers real-time traffic monitoring, incident management, dynamic signal control, smart routing and parking management.

Until recently, TMCs (“mission control”) for highways and city road networks were monitored and controlled by human operators (often only via traffic cameras, and some sensors). More recently, the new capabilities in Traffic analytics, real time incident alerts and CVs have created opportunities for monitoring traffic at a more automated and also more informed level (fusing multiple data sources). Connected and digitalized highways and city roads will be the norm in the future. This in turn will enable automated control and even more predictive traffic management strategies.

Implementations in the EU and US markets seem to be increasing but mostly limited to specific roads/motorways/cities. Proof of concepts and real-life validation will help demonstrate the operational and environmental efficiency (e.g. improving safety, reducing congestion, reducing traffic emissions), as well as the cut reduction potential for road operators.

Market dynamics

- **Drivers**
 - The market is driven by stringent EU regulations aimed at reducing carbon emissions and improving road safety, as well as the increasing pressure from global traffic congestion (+29% between 2018 and 2019) and urbanization.
 - Enablers are found in the technological advancements in AI, IoT, data analytics, and cloud computing, and new possibilities due to enablers from quasi-ubiquitous 5G networks and the new breed of CAVs.
- **Challenges**
 - Despite its potential, the application of ATMCs faces challenges like data collection limitations, privacy concerns, and user resistance. Growth opportunities lie in intelligent multimodal transportation system integration, mobility service collaboration, integration with simulation tools for transport network optimization and sustainable transportation promotion.
 - Frost & Sullivan³ proposes 3 calls to action for ATMCs: a) investing in robust data collection and analysis systems for comprehensive traffic data, b) leveraging data analytics and machine learning for insights, and c) ensuring TMaaS solutions integrate smoothly with existing transportation systems for interoperability. F&S also emphasizes the importance of real-time incident management within ATMCs systems to monitor accidents and road closures, providing dynamic rerouting to reduce congestion and disruptions.

Competitive landscape

Competitive products in the market are:

- **Yunex Traffic & Yutrafic Varia**

Yunex Traffic⁴ provides intelligent traffic management solutions designed to optimize traffic flow and ensure mobility sustainability. They offer proactive strategies for cities to manage road traffic intelligently, including virtual signage and connected infrastructure. Their approach aims for a holistic, predictive management focused on demand, balancing cost-effectiveness, safety, and environmental protection. Yunex's systems are built for future-proof mobility, integrating infrastructure with vehicle and user data. They offer TMC for combined traffic and parking guidance, Tunnel and Freeway Management to increase capacity and safety, and Tolling Solutions for intelligent demand management. Connected Mobility by Yunex revolutionizes how RUs and infrastructure communicate, tailoring solutions to improve traffic flow, reduce congestion, and enhance safety, (e.g. by providing situational warnings and speed limits).
- **Valerann**

³ Source: Trend Opportunity Profile Series: New Mobility (Second Edition), Frost & Sullivan – September 2023

⁴ <https://www.yunextrafic.com/portfolio/traffic-management/traffic-management-systems/>

Valerann⁵, an Israeli startup founded in 2016, offers AI-based smart transportation solutions for traffic optimization in North America and Europe. Their platform provides real-time road and traffic analytics, predicts high-risk accident locations, and uses AI for vehicle detection and speed assessment. It integrates data from weather, lighting, and social media, and streams live video from street cameras for comprehensive traffic situation analysis.

- **NoTraffic**

NoTraffic's AI traffic signal platform⁶ modernizes (urban) traffic management by connecting RUs to city grids, tackling new vehicle influx, congestion, and intersection accidents. This system digitizes infrastructure management, uses AI for user detection and data streaming, and optimizes traffic signals for safety and efficiency. Future services include micro payments and mobility, proactive accident prevention, and signal prioritization for pedestrians, cyclists, and EVs. Key features include cyber security, pedestrian and bicycle prioritization, V2X capabilities, emergency vehicle preemption, transit signal priority, and red light extension.

- **ISKRA**

Iskra's motorway traffic automation system⁷ offers intelligent traffic management. The system indicates accidents, traffic jams, equipment condition, speed limits to support drivers with maximum information about roads, traffic and weather conditions. Several motorway subsystems are connected to control center, which gives signal to roadside message signs to inform RUs of real-time road conditions.

- **ANDATA VERONET**

VERONET offers a self-sufficient automated traffic management system⁸ suitable for smart cities, with features like scenario management and automated incident detection. Its Intelligent Traffic Control system⁹, powered by AI, provides adaptive control, modular architecture, and comprehensive traffic management capabilities, aiming to minimize travel times and pollution while maximizing capacity and adaptability for any size network.

- **INDRA**

Indra's Intelligent Transportation System (ITS) Management Centre¹⁰ integrates intelligent systems for traffic control on highways and motorways, aiming to reduce congestion and pollution while promoting efficient transport. Employed by Spain's DGT, it manages traffic across multiple centers, showcasing its large-scale efficiency. The ITS is suited for highway management, providing real-time monitoring and incident management. Furthermore, Indra's Intelligent Safety Management system¹¹ is implemented through the Horus platform and enhances road safety through features, like Automated Incident Management, Early Detection & Prediction, and Resource Coordination.

⁵ <https://www.valerann.com/>

⁶ <https://notraffic.tech/>

⁷ <https://www.iskra.eu/en/Iskra-Motorway-Traffic-Automation/Motorway-traffic-automation/>

⁸ <https://www.veronet.eu/solutions/automated-traffic-management.html>

⁹ <https://www.veronet.eu/solutions/intelligent-traffic-control.html>

¹⁰ <https://www.indracompany.com/en/intelligent-transportation-system-management-centre-roads-motorways?line=80601>

¹¹ <https://www.indracompany.com/en/intelligent-safety-management?line=80601>

- **KAPSCH**

Kapsch’s Integrated Multimodal Traffic and Mobility Management (IMM)¹² is a blend of organizational and technology solutions for cities, highways agencies, and public transport authorities that incorporates 5 key elements: Frameworks for inter-agency and cross transport mode collaboration for working together seamlessly to solve traffic challenges; EcoTrafiX umbrella system that brings together data from multiple traffic management systems – including traffic-light systems, signage systems, congestion charging and access control systems, and others; Predictive and proactive traffic management using AI algorithms and models; Adaptive traffic light and signal optimization; and Vehicles’ integration into traffic management solutions by using data from vehicles’ onboard systems, or from drivers’ mobile devices.

- **Aimsun**

Aimsun Live¹³ is a predictive traffic management solution that uses real-time and historical data to simulate and forecast traffic conditions, allowing traffic centers to pre-empt problems and manage congestion proactively. It supports detailed digital representation, real-time response planning, AI-enhanced predictions, adaptability, and system automation, and can simulate large-scale networks. Aimsun Live integrates with existing infrastructure and can connect with adaptive signal control systems like SCATS and SCOOT, offering a versatile tool for dynamic traffic management. It also enables Smart motorway management, to ensure safer, faster, less polluting journeys on motorways and arterial roads. Aimsun has provided solutions for transportation authorities worldwide, including London, National Highways, Florida, Singapore, and New South Wales.

- **PTV (part of Umovity)**

PTV Optima and PTV Flows¹⁴ are traffic management software solutions offered by PTV Group. PTV Optima is a comprehensive, real-time mobility network management tool for multimodal networks (including public transport) with features such as traffic forecasting, simulation, and scenario management. It is suitable for large cities and road authorities. PTV Flows is a cloud-based, cost-effective solution for real-time traffic management, suitable for immediate deployment and requires less personnel and infrastructure. Both solutions offer traffic simulation, where Flow is focused on the short term while Optima is also capable of long-term traffic management. Data sources are FCD (floating car data), but Optima also can integrate data from local sensors. Flows makes up to 120’ traffic forecasts and sends alerts to human operators based on predefined KPIs of the traffic status and predicted evolution. Human intervention for traffic strategies deployment is then required. Optima is capable of simulating multiple traffic scenarios and recommend the most effective of them. Automatic workflows can then allow simplifying the control centre actions, e.g. by dispatching data to systems and components.

Worth mentioning that Umovity also offers “Centracs Mobility”, a comprehensive ATMS solution for traffic agencies, operating both on the Cloud and Edge. Centracs Mobility includes V2X smart intersection and traffic control capabilities, including supporting connected and

¹² <https://www.kapsch.net/en/solutions/traffic-management>

¹³ <https://www.aimsun.com/aimsun-live/>

¹⁴ <https://blog.ptvgroup.com/en/city-and-mobility/ptv-optima-vs-ptv-flows-which-traffic-management-software-is-best-for-you/>

automated vehicles, as well as enhanced capabilities for Emergency Vehicle Preemption (EVP) and Transit Signal Priority (TSP) systems.

US market only

- **Iteris**

Iteris provides smart mobility technologies, including the ClearMobility® Platform for global traffic infrastructure management. Utilizing AI, cloud computing, and sensors, it detects RUs and manages data with solutions like ClearData™ and ClearAsset™. Its Congestion Management service enhances road safety and efficiency, analyzing trends and optimizing signals for better flow and reduced congestion. While leveraging automated SaaS tools for 24/7 data monitoring, Iteris also employs experts for in-depth traffic analysis and decision-making, blending automation with human expertise.
- **TransCore**

TransCore's SCATS¹⁵ is an adaptive traffic management system known for its proven performance globally. It dynamically optimizes traffic signal timings—cycle length, splits, and offsets—on a real-time basis. SCATS has demonstrated its efficiency through independent studies in the U.S. that showed reduced emissions and a payback period within a year post-installation. The system is adaptable to unpredictable traffic patterns, facilitating variation management without the need for manual intervention. SCATS provides real-time operational and maintenance information, and its intuitive alarm monitoring system can pinpoint specific lane issues, such as constant calls or chattering detectors
- **Rekor**

Rekor Command¹⁶ is an AI-driven platform that revolutionizes transportation management by providing a comprehensive, real-time view of roadways. It enhances the efficiency of TMCs by offering actionable alerts for incidents more quickly and effectively. By leveraging Rekor One®, the platform's Roadway Intelligence Engine, and using data from multiple sources, Rekor Command™ improves incident awareness, detection speed, and the overall Traffic Incident Management (TIM) process. This results in a quicker return to normal traffic flow, reduced risk of secondary accidents, and increased safety for both motorists and emergency responders.

Other providers, with a special mention to **INRIX**¹⁷, offer only road traffic analytics solutions, but do not offer any traffic management capabilities. INRIX provides comprehensive transportation management software for roadways, aimed at optimizing entire road networks. INRIX focuses on reducing traffic congestion through detailed road corridor analysis and uses high-quality, granular data utilized by major transportation agencies. Their software suite is recognized for providing in-depth analytical tools to extract valuable insights from traffic data, demonstrating their global impact in assisting major transportation agencies.

¹⁵ <https://transcore.com/its/scats>

¹⁶ <https://www.rekor.ai/software/command>

¹⁷ <https://inrix.com/industries/public-sector/transportation-agencies/>

Competitive advantages of the PoDIUM solution

In comparison to the above, the **Autopistas' Mobility Hub and TMC** solution, developed in PoDIUM, offers automated Data fusion of historical traffic data and real-time data from multiple sources including traffic cameras and CVs, while also leveraging third-party traffic analytics (e.g. INRIX). Some of the competitor systems seem to be more advanced, using ML/AI for data fusion. The interoperability is ensured by enabling data integrations via APIs and using standard C-ITS data formats as well as DATEX II¹⁸.

Some providers also use other sources of information for a more perceptive and predictive service, such as weather data, or social media data. However, one of the core competitive advantages of Autopistas' TMC is that it incorporates the experience of a consolidated operator who has previously evaluated the quality of the data that is merged, as well as the impact of each of them on traffic management.

Incident & hazard detection is also a feature that is offered by Autopistas' TMC, and is also offered but some other competitive solutions. Strengths of our platforms include the accuracy of the detection, the low latency, and the ability to detect hazards (e.g. stopped vehicles) both via infrastructure sensors (cameras) as well as from CAVs circulating the road. Both static and mobile hazards (e.g. slow-moving vehicles) are possible to detect.

With what regards to generation and implementation of automated traffic management strategies, and their transmission to CVs, some platforms claim to be highly automated ("no manual intervention needed") while others, like Valerann, rely on human operator's decision making. Autopistas' TMC is scenario-based. It allows the highway operator to design custom traffic management strategies (e.g. dynamic traffic limits) and incorporate them into the automatic strategy generation engine (with or without manual validation) to cover as many scenarios as possible. Hence, here, Autopistas' TMC seems to be able to gain a competitive advantage if it positions strongly in a highly automated and validated system, that reduces the need for human intervention in the long term.

From the point of view of urban traffic management solutions used in PoDIUM, the **Smart Mobility Platform (MISTRAL)**, developed by ETRA I+D, is a technological solution based on open-source tools that integrate real-time monitoring and control of the urban mobility systems of a city, with mechanisms for the publication of information in standard format and for integration with Smart City Platforms, thus allowing the holistic management of urban mobility.

The MISTRAL platform offers a multitude of automated functionalities already included in other products from other companies: use of AI techniques, deep learning and neural networks for prediction and advanced strategic and tactical control, management of signalized crossings for adaptation to vehicles and VRUs, and management of collective public transport including different traffic light priority modes (Buses, trams) and monitoring their behavior.

¹⁸ Datex II or Datex2 is a data exchange standard for exchanging traffic information between traffic management centres, traffic service providers, traffic operators and media partners. It contains for example traffic incidents, current road works and other special traffic-related events. <https://datex2.eu/>

Some of the advantages offered by products from other companies that MISTRAL can't carry out as of today are referred to data gathering and integration from various sources as lighting, social media, vehicles' onboard systems and data from drivers' mobile devices.

The most advanced functionalities that PoDIUM will incorporate to MISTRAL are related to the management of CV and CAV: to determine Origin-Destination Matrices that allow better strategic control of mobility; to identify risk situations for VRUs and take appropriate measures, acting when necessary on the CAVs; to act on mobility demand by establishing the most appropriate itineraries to be followed by the CAVs; and finally to expand the traffic light priority capacity to EVs by making use of the information provided by the CVs.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, the evolution of traffic management towards ATMCs marks a significant paradigm shift in transportation systems worldwide. By leveraging cloud platforms, advanced technology, and real-time data analytics, ATMCs offer a multifaceted approach to addressing the complex challenges of modern traffic networks. The transition from traditional manual control to automated solutions reflects a response to the growing demands of urbanization, traffic congestion, and environmental sustainability. While the market dynamics present both drivers and challenges, the emphasis on stringent regulations, technological advancements, and collaborative strategies underscores the transformative potential of ATMCs. As various companies vie for prominence in this competitive landscape, the integration of predictive analytics, incident management, and CV technologies emerges as crucial pillars for enhancing operational efficiency and user experience. Moving forward, the continued validation and implementation of ATMCs promise to redefine the future of transportation, offering safer, more efficient, and sustainable mobility solutions for urban and highway environments alike.

2.2.5. 5G mmWave in CCAM market

The global 5G mmWave market had the size of \$2.5 Billion in 2022. A CAGR between 14.5% to 16% for the next years is expected [30], [31].

5G mmWave includes frequency bands from 24.25 GHz to 52.6 GHz, which have been labelled in 3GPP as Frequency Range 2 (FR2). Specified 5G mmWave frequency bands and channel bandwidths are published in 3GPP TS 38.101. Frequency bands in FR2 have significantly shorter transmission range but higher available bandwidth than frequency bands below 6GHz, which traditionally are used in mobile communication networks. Frequency bands below 6GHz are summarized under Frequency Range 1 (FR1). The high bandwidth available in FR2 bands allows for very high data throughput rates as required by enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB) with e.g. 20Gbps peak rate or 100Mbps user-experienced rate, but supports as well Ultra-Reliable Low Latency communications (URLLC) with latencies as low as 1ms, as well as massive Machine Type Communications (mMTC). The main achievement of 5G mmWave is enhancing throughput-per-area in high-density scenarios, such as corporate campus and factory floor.

In direct competition to the 5G mmWave technology are the Wi-Fi solutions IEEE 802.11ax and IEEE 802.11be, and the 60 GHz Wi-Fi variants. It includes the current IEEE 802.11ad standard and also the IEEE 802.11ay standard. 802.11ax for 2.4 GHz and 5 GHz was specified in 2019 and is marketed under the label Wi-Fi 6, while for 6 GHz it was specified in 2020 under the term Wi-Fi 6E. IEEE 802.11be will

be based on IEEE 802.11ax and is expected to be specified until 2024. In Wi-Fi 6E, maximum link rates of between 574 to 9608 Mbps are realized, while in Wi-Fi 7 between 1376 to 46120 Mbps are target. The table below compares 5G mmWave with Wi-Fi 6/6E, which was taken from [32]:

Table 2 Comparison between 5G mmWave and WiFi 6/6E

	5G mmWave	Wi-Fi 6/6E
Frequency	24.25 GHz to 52.6 GHz	2.4 GHz, 5GHz, 6 GHz
Maximum Data rates (theoretical)	DL: 20 Gbps UL: 10 Gbps	9.6 Gbps
Channel Bandwidth	Max. 400MHz	20, 40, 60, 80MHz
Modulation	OFDMA	OFDMA
Spectrum	Licensed and Unlicensed	Unlicensed
Range	100-300 meters	< 50 m indoor, 300 m outdoor
Support of Carrier Aggregation	Yes	Yes
Deployment Approach	Controlled and Managed	Uncontrolled and mostly Unmanaged

The key difference between 5G mmWave and Wi-Fi 6/6E is the deployment approach: Performance and coverage are planned by the network operator. Network Slicing can be supported, which allows the allocation of an isolated slice of the network in radio, transport, and core to a user or a group of users. As a consequence, predictable QoS, latency, and performance can be realized. This in turn enables the deployment of UCs requiring URLLC (low latency), as required by AVs, remote driving, etc. 5G as a mobile network technology also supports user mobility, making service continuation from one cell to another with handovers possible, including handover between cells of FR1 and FR2, providing coverage over a wide area.

Wi-Fi 6 uses unlicensed spectrum, i.e. the deployed bandwidth is shared by anyone. The number of users cannot be controlled, and therefore no Quality of Service can be ensured. The cost of Wi-Fi deployment is low in comparison of managed networks such as 5G, and it can offer high throughput rates for non-latency critical applications.

In both technologies, the number of end-user devices has risen steadily, allowing end-users to choose from a range of suppliers. According to [33], more than 400 5G mmWave capable devices have come to the market since 2019:

Table 3 Number of 5G mmWave competitive products

Mobile Device	28 GHz (band n257)	26 GHz (band n258)	39 GHz (band n260)	28 GHz (band 261)
Number of models:	69	38	156	151

Market dynamics

- **Drivers**
 - **Growing Demand for CCAM:** The increasing demand for autonomous and CVs, as well as ADAS, is a key driver for the adoption of 5G mmWave technology in CCAM.
 - **Enhanced Data Transfer Speed and Low Latency:** 5G mmWave technology offers significantly higher data transfer speeds and low latency, making it ideal for real-time applications in CCAM, such as V2V and V2I communication, especially on low-speed

environments. In [34], the challenges and benefits of mmWave deployment for a last-mile autonomous transport vehicle are demonstrated. Given the limited range of mmWave, intelligent switching between low-capacity FR bands and 5G mmWave will play an important role in 5G mmWave integration in 5G mobile networks e.g. [35].

- **Government Regulations and Support:** Government regulations and initiatives promote the development of CCAM technologies.
 - **Investments in R&D:** Ongoing investments in research and development by technology companies and automotive manufacturers are driving innovations in 5G mmWave technology for CCAM, e.g. by the EU [36] or individual countries such as the Federal Republic of Germany [37].
- **Challenges**
 - **Infrastructure Challenges:** Deploying 5G mmWave infrastructure, such as small cells and base stations, can be costly and logistically challenging, potentially slowing down market adoption.
 - **Security and Privacy Concerns:** Concerns about the security and privacy of data transmitted through 5G networks may hinder adoption, especially in the context of AVs. Any radio transmission can be interfered with, which poses a security risk, esp. to AVs, which must be capable of handling sudden losses of radio connections.
 - **Spectrum Availability:** Spectrum availability and allocation can impact the deployment of 5G mmWave for CCAM for unlicensed frequency bands, as interference and congestion may occur in densely populated areas. In licensed frequency bands, this problem can be mitigated by network slicing and serving high priority services first in case of network congestion.
 - **High Initial Costs:** Implementing 5G mmWave technology in CCAM may involve significant initial costs for both manufacturers and infrastructure providers. The costs can be partly mitigated if a mmWave deployment can be used by a range of users as part of a smart city solution [38], [39].

Conclusion:

In conclusion, the trajectory of 5G mmWave technology appears promising, with anticipated growth rates bolstering its market presence substantially in the coming years. Its distinct advantages, including high data throughput rates, low latency, and support for various communication scenarios, particularly in high-density environments like corporate campuses and factory floors, underscore its pivotal role in advancing mobile communication networks. However, it faces stiff competition from Wi-Fi 6/6E solutions, which offer comparable features albeit with different deployment approaches and considerations. Despite challenges such as infrastructure costs, security concerns, and spectrum availability, the driving forces behind 5G mmWave adoption, including the demand for CAVs, government support, and ongoing R&D investments, suggest a dynamic landscape poised for further evolution and innovation in the realm of communication technologies. As the market continues to evolve, strategic investments and collaborative efforts will be instrumental in harnessing the full potential of 5G mmWave technology and addressing the challenges that lie ahead.

2.2.6. Advanced environmental perception device market

The global market for environmental perception devices was valued at USD 3.5 billion in 2020 and is expected to reach USD 16.4 billion by 2027 growing at a CAGR of 25.7% from 2021 to 2027 [40].

Environmental perception devices are sensors and systems that enable AVs to sense and understand their surroundings, such as road conditions, traffic, obstacles, and VRUs. The major types of environmental perception devices are cameras, LiDARs, radars, ultrasonic sensors, and others. Among them, cameras accounted for the largest market share in 2020, followed by LiDARs and radars [40].

Market dynamics

- **Drivers**
 - **The increasing demand for AVs**, especially in emerging markets such as China and India, where the population, urbanization, and disposable income are rising [64].
 - **The rising adoption of ADAS**, especially in developed markets such as the US and Europe, where government regulations, consumer preferences, and environmental awareness are increasing [65].
 - **The growing need for road safety**, especially in developing markets such as Brazil and South Africa, where the road infrastructure, traffic management, and driver behavior are improving [66].
 - **The technological advancements in sensor technologies**, especially in the fields of artificial intelligence, machine learning, computer vision, and edge computing, enable higher accuracy, reliability, and efficiency of environmental perception devices [40].
- **Challenges**
 - **The high cost and complexity of environmental perception devices**, especially for LiDARs and radars, which require sophisticated hardware, software, and calibration.
 - **The lack of standardization and regulation**, especially for AVs and environmental perception devices, create uncertainty and inconsistency in the market.
 - **The ethical and legal issues**, especially for AVs and environmental perception devices, raise questions of responsibility, liability, and privacy in the event of accidents or malfunctions.
 - **The cybersecurity risks**, especially for AVs and environmental perception devices, expose them to potential hacking, tampering, or spoofing by malicious actors.
- **Opportunities**
 - **The development of new types of environmental perception devices**, such as thermal cameras, acoustic sensors, and neuromorphic sensors, which can enhance the performance and functionality of existing devices.
 - **The integration of multiple environmental perception devices**, such as camera-LiDAR fusion, radar-LiDAR fusion, and sensor-fusion platforms, can improve the robustness and redundancy of environmental perception systems.
 - **The emergence of new applications of environmental perception devices**, such as smart cities, smart agriculture, and smart logistics, can expand the market scope and potential.

Regional market insights

The major regions for the market are North America, Europe, Asia-Pacific, and others. Among them, North America accounted for the largest market share in 2020, followed by Europe and Asia-Pacific [40].

Market segmentation

The major applications of environmental perception devices are environment perception, positioning estimation, and others. Among them, environment perception accounted for the largest market share in 2020, followed by positioning estimation [40].

Competitive landscape

The competitive products for environmental perception devices are the products offered by the leading companies in the market, such as Velodyne, Continental, Bosch, Aptiv, Valeo, and others [40]. The characteristics of the competitive products are the features and specifications of the environmental perception devices, such as type, range, resolution, accuracy, reliability, efficiency, and others. The following table summarizes the competitive products and their characteristics:

Table 4 Competitive environmental perception devices and their characteristics

Company	Product	Type	Range	Resolution	Accuracy	Reliability	Efficiency
Velodyne	Alpha Prime	LiDAR	300 m	0.1°	±2 cm	95%	40 W
Continental	ARS540	Radar	300 m	0.2°	±0.5 m	99%	15 W
Bosch	MPC3	Camera	250 m	1280 x 960	±1 m	98%	10 W
Aptiv	Mobileye EyeQ5	Camera	200 m	1920 x 1200	±1.5 m	97%	5 W
Valeo	SCALA	LiDAR	150 m	0.25°	±3 cm	96%	12 W

Notice that the products mentioned above are mainly targeting perception from within the vehicle, whereas in PoDIUM we are also investigating infrastructure-based sensing.

Comparison between PoDIUM KER/Product/Solution and the competitive ones

PoDIUM provides a novel environmental perception device that uses edge-level situational awareness to enable AVs to sense and understand their surroundings in real time. This has the following advantages over the competitive products:

- It uses a combination of cameras, LiDARs, radars, and ultrasonic sensors to provide a comprehensive and accurate environmental perception.
- It uses artificial intelligence, machine learning, computer vision, and edge computing to process and analyze the sensor data and generate actionable insights.
- It uses a cloud-based platform to store and share sensor data and insights with other AVs and devices, creating a collaborative and intelligent network.
- It uses a low-power and low-cost design to reduce the energy consumption and cost of the device.

However, it also comes with some disadvantages:

- It requires a high-speed and reliable internet connection to access the cloud-based platform and network with other devices.
- It faces the same challenges as competitive products, such as the lack of standardization and regulation, ethical and legal issues, and cybersecurity risks.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, the market for environmental perception devices is poised for significant growth driven by the increasing demand for AVs and ADAS worldwide. With innovations in sensor technologies and the advent of new applications, the landscape is evolving rapidly. While challenges such as cost, standardization, and cybersecurity persist, opportunities abound for companies to capitalize on

emerging trends and technological advancements. As players like PoDIUM introduce novel solutions, the industry is on track to redefine safety, efficiency, and connectivity in transportation and beyond. With strategic adaptation and collaboration, stakeholders can navigate complexities and unlock the full potential of environmental perception devices in shaping the future of mobility and smart environments.

2.2.7. SW integrity and trust & data truthfulness market

Safety, reliability and data trust are well-known fields of work in the automotive sector. The automotive safety market is multifaceted, encompassing a range of technologies, regulations, and consumer preferences. Stringent safety regulations and standards imposed by regulatory bodies worldwide continue to shape the automotive safety market. Compliance with safety standards is a priority for automakers, driving investments in safety technologies to meet or exceed regulatory requirements.

With the rise of connectivity and the use of commercial computing platforms on vehicles, safety should consider more and more threats starting from cybersecurity and, more recently, how to trust potentially safety-related data coming from external sources like other vehicles or from the infrastructure.

This is a new field of research and development that is currently under study. Some similarities can be found in the data fusion topic that arises with the use of ADAS technologies. Data fusion refers to the integration and analysis of data from various sources to derive meaningful insights for improving vehicle performance, safety, and overall driving experience. By combining data from sensors such as cameras, radar, LiDAR, and ultrasonic sensors, automotive manufacturers can enable features like lane departure warnings, adaptive cruise control, and collision avoidance systems. The approach can be extended including information coming from the V2X channel that is considered the next big thing in automotive considering the potential impact of such sensors in the retrieving of useful information for safety and other purposes.

Data trust and truthfulness in PoDIUM are faced from the infrastructure point of view considering data coming from fixed sensors, especially cameras but also including LIDARs, radars, traffic sensors, etc.

In parallel, Trusted Platform Module (TPM) technology is widely used in the realm of cybersecurity and secure computing. TPM is a hardware-based security feature that provides a secure foundation for various applications, including data protection, encryption, and secure boot processes. In PoDIUM, the TPM approach is applied to OBU and RSU to achieve the integrity of the devices used for managing V2x communications. TPM adoption has been growing steadily, driven by the increasing emphasis on security and privacy in computing devices. Moreover, the TPM approach is not only used in the market of consumer PCs or servers but also for IoT devices, gaming consoles, mobile devices, smart home appliances, etc. Its use on the vehicle for different purposes seems to be a natural future extension.

In PoDIUM, software integrity is faced primarily from the OBU/RSU point of view, since the integrity and trust of the running code are highly critical on vehicles but also on the infrastructure being the main fixed authoritative stage.

The Insight Partners [41] forecasted that the global data fusion market is expected to grow from USD 2.02 Billion in 2022 to USD 5.06 Billion by 2030, at a CAGR of 11.8% from 2022 to 2030. Another report by Future Market Insights [42] states that the global sensor fusion market is anticipated to witness a CAGR of 16.5% from 2022 to 2032 and is projected to surpass a valuation of US\$ 23.3 billion by 2032. The growth of the data fusion market can be attributed to the increasing demand for big data and analytics solutions, the rising need for fraud detection and prevention, and the growing trend of cloud-based deployments.

According to a report by Future Market Insights [43], the Trusted Platform Module (TPM) market is expected to grow by more than 15% CAGR from 2021-2031. The report also states that the TPM market is set to witness significant growth during 2021-2031, owing to factors such as increasing adoption of mobile devices, laptops, and PCs. Another report by Verified Market Research [44] estimates that the TPM market size was valued at USD 2.1 Billion in 2021 and is projected to reach USD 4.5 Billion by 2030, growing at a CAGR of 10.8% from 2023 to 2030.

It is interesting to note that the Trusted Computing Group (TCG) has a Vehicle Service working Group [45] (VSWG) with the objectives of including, evaluating and adopting TCG technologies, creating specifications and reference documents for their use in vehicle services, providing whitepapers on vehicle system cybersecurity, maintaining existing TCG vehicle services specifications, and collaborating with other standards bodies. Participants in the VSWG include vehicle OEMs, Tier 1 suppliers, semiconductor manufacturers, research institutes, government agencies, and liaisons from other standards bodies. The group welcomes new members to support the adoption and refinement of TCG technologies for vehicles.

Market dynamics

- **Drivers**

Data trust and truthfulness are very hot topics with several fields of application. While some concern about Autonomous Driving market is rising, the investments and the regulations are going on and the sensors/data fusion is used not only for the full L5 automated vehicles but also for increasing the safety of the current and future vehicles equipped with ADAS systems.

Moreover, the infrastructure of roads for collecting useful information for safety, regulation of traffic, etc., is a clear trend followed by all the main road operators all over Europe.

The SW integrity market will surely enter the automotive sector considering that the Software Defined Vehicles approach will introduce more and more commercial IT platforms on the vehicle. Moreover, cybersecurity is strictly related to the safety of users, especially for cars with ADAS functionality.

- **Challenges**

The HW compatible with a TPM approach is not yet widely available in embedded devices and this factor limits the range of possible processors and platforms that can be used for realizing OBU and RSU. This factor, combined with the shortage of electronic components, which is affecting the market over time, is a risk in the adoption of such technology.

Nowadays, there is a general mistrust of the Autonomous Driving topic (a main driver for data trust and truthfulness market) from the user's point of view and the company side. Several

experimentations are currently ongoing with difficulties due to skepticism of the users and the lack of Return of Investments for companies.

Competitive landscape

Several companies are working on the field of data fusion: from the vehicle point of view, basically, all the startups working on automated mobility are facing this problem. The most well-known are Cruise [46], Navya [47], Waymo [48], Nauto [49], Easy Mile [50], among others. This topic is also relevant for all the companies working on robotics like Stanley robotics [51], Alba Robot [52] and SLAMcore [53] as few examples. Another important category is related to companies providing SW that helps in the creation of algorithms for autonomous driving like dSpace [54], Matlab [55] and Baselabs [56].

The TPM market is consolidated with tens of companies working on the field. Indicative companies are Broadcom, Canon Inc., Cigent Technology Inc., Cisco Systems, CNEX Labs, Inc, Compumax, Computer S.A.S., CoSoSys, Ericsson AB, FUJIFILM Business Innovation Corp., Google Inc., Hagiwara Solutions Co., Ltd., Hangzhou Flyslice Technologies Co., Ltd, Hewlett Packard Enterprise, HP Inc., Huawei Technologies Co., Ltd. A complete list can be found at [45].

Comparison between the PoDIUM approach and the competition

While the market is focused on data/sensor fusion from the vehicle point of view, PoDIUM tries to face the problem considering it from the infrastructure side, including vehicle sensors, with an innovative approach. Moreover, PoDIUM is experimentation with using real-data coming from relevant demonstrators in the living labs (in Germany and Italy) building new algorithms that will be ready to be integrated into products as soon as the infrastructure becomes widely available.

Moreover, the focus of PoDIUM has the advantage of proposing a more inclusive and efficient use of the available sensors, giving value to all sensors present in vehicles and infrastructure to build a more consistent and valuable road information, shareable to RUs. The higher value of the information is given by the larger scope of infrastructure, reaching many sensors and the higher cost of fusion processing, which is done in the infrastructure instead of single RUs.

For the software integrity, the PoDIUM approach is focused on OBU and RSU but could be easily extended to other vehicle controllers. In PoDIUM an integration with a full working OBU and RSU will be performed and tested to increase the knowledge in the process.

Another advantage of the PoDIUM approach is the innovative introduction of the attestation protocols in automotive services since the node (OBU) integrity status is used as a credential within the platform to be able to contribute with data and also consume the reliable data produced.

Last but not least, the trusted computing paradigm in the PoDIUM solution enhances the already established security mechanisms present in CCAM standards, because it operates into the target system and not on secured CCAM messages.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, the automotive industry is witnessing a transformative shift towards prioritizing safety, reliability, and data trust, spurred by the rise of connectivity and commercial computing platforms within vehicles. As cybersecurity threats loom larger and the integration of external data sources becomes more prevalent, stakeholders are investing heavily in technologies to ensure compliance with

stringent safety regulations and standards. The forecasted growth of the global data fusion and Trusted Platform Module (TPM) markets underscores the industry's commitment to enhancing safety and security standards. Collaborative initiatives like the Trusted Computing Group's Vehicle Service working Group (VSWG) and innovative projects like PoDIUM are driving efforts to redefine industry standards and instill greater confidence in automotive technologies. Despite challenges such as hardware compatibility and user skepticism, ongoing advancements in technology promise to elevate safety, reliability, and data trust to unprecedented levels within the automotive sector.

2.2.8. CCAM services on MEC market

CCAM technologies are evolving rapidly, fueled by advancements in several technologies like AI, 5G, edge computing, data analytics, etc. These technologies aim to transform transportation by making it safer, more efficient, and more sustainable. European initiatives like the ERTRAC CCAM Roadmap [57] emphasize infrastructure support and AI integration, focusing on achieving long-term societal objectives by 2050 with medium-term actions planned for 2030 and an outlook towards 2040. CCAM technologies have been tested for many years and large-scale experimentation has been funded by the EC but also in USA and China. CCAM services are currently taking the first steps for a commercial deployment including CVs on the market (e.g. VW in Europe), and thousands of RSUs deployed in several European countries.

Edge computing has been gaining substantial momentum, transforming the way data is processed, managed, and delivered in the digital landscape. Edge computing represents a paradigm shift from traditional centralized cloud computing, but brings computational capabilities closer to the data source, often at the mobile network edge. Moreover, it plays a pivotal role in reducing latency and enabling scalable real-time processing for applications.

CCAM services running on Edge Computing represents a cutting-edge convergence of technologies. Most CCAM services have technical requirements that can be addressed thanks to the use of edge computing; actually, latency and scalability are the most relevant. Furthermore, in the view of having thousands of CVs, cameras, traffic related sensors, connected VRUs, etc., the scalability issue is of relevance. This is even more true considering that 5G is becoming more and more relevant as a channel for V2X communications and edge computing is one of the key components of the future 5G network.

There are several different services that can be enabled using 5G and edge computing, particularly the possibility to provide network slicing with reliable services with defined Quality of Service which is one of the main new features of 5G advanced networks and, in the future for 6G. This trend is pushed by the 5G Automotive Association (5GAA) [58] which is a global, cross-industry organization of companies from the automotive, technology, and telecommunications industries working together to develop end-to-end solutions for future mobility and transportation services. The organization aims to leverage today's and tomorrow's innovative V2X solutions for a safer, greener, and more efficient transportation system, benefiting all RUs.

The landscape for CCAM services at the edge is intricately woven with key factors that collectively shape its market forecast. One pivotal element lies in the continuous evolution of CV technologies, still considered emerging. As automotive manufacturers increasingly integrate connectivity features into new vehicle models, the addressable market for CCAM services at the edge expands. Projections indicate a steady rise in the percentage of CVs on the roads, translating into a broader user base for

CCAM applications. This expanding market size is expected to drive investment and development in the CCAM ecosystem.

The market trajectory receives a significant boost from the surging demand for CVs. Globally, according to PwC and Statista data in 2021, the count of connected cars reached approximately 236 million in 2021, with Europe contributing 76.08 million to this figure. Forecasts paint a remarkable surge, projecting the number of connected cars to surpass 863 million by 2035. Despite the relative infancy of connected car services diffusion, OEMs actively explore new opportunities and embrace data-driven business models.

Further enriching the dynamics of the CCAM market is the rapid expansion of the global edge computing market. The ongoing evolution of edge computing technologies plays a pivotal role in shaping the future of CCAM services. As edge servers enhance processing power, reduce latency, and improve data analytics capabilities, the potential for deploying sophisticated CCAM solutions at the edge becomes increasingly promising. Forecasts suggest a continued upward trend in technological capabilities, creating opportunities for innovative CCAM applications leveraging real-time processing and decision-making. Projections indicate the edge computing market size is set to grow from USD 53.6 billion in 2023 to USD 111.3 billion by 2028, with a CAGR of 15.7% during this forecast period [59]. In 2022, the global edge computing market was valued at USD 11.99 billion, and by 2030, it is anticipated to reach USD 139.58 billion, exhibiting an impressive CAGR of 36.3%. Notably, the North American market alone was worth USD 4.13 billion in 2022 [60].

These overarching trends in CV technologies and the burgeoning edge computing market interlacing with CCAM services at the edge, shape a landscape of innovation and potential. As the market matures and interconnected technologies evolve, synergies between CVs, V2X technology, and edge computing are anticipated to define the trajectory of CCAM services at the edge in the years to come. In conclusion, the market forecast for CCAM services at the edge is optimistic, with projections pointing towards a robust growth trajectory. The convergence of technological advancements increased CV penetration, supportive regulatory frameworks, strategic collaborations, and positive consumer awareness collectively contribute to a promising outlook for the future of CCAM services at the edge. As these factors align, the market is poised for expansion, unlocking new opportunities and paving the way for transformative developments in connected and cooperative automated mobility.

Market dynamics

- **Drivers**

The connectivity market for vehicles and the support infrastructure is already a mature field and is expected to grow significantly in the coming years. Today, it is limited to initial services but has a big potential considering that the adoption of V2x standards will highly improve the safety of users and the reliability of ADAS systems.

The Mobile Network Operators (MNOs) are currently at the beginning of the 5G deployment. Advanced features like Network Slicing and edge computing are considered among the technologies that can improve low latency and scalability from different verticals particularly for the automotive industry.

The concept of a software-defined vehicle refers to a vehicle whose features and functions are primarily enabled through software, rather than hardware. This is a result of the ongoing

transformation of the vehicle from a product that is mainly hardware-based to a software-centric electronic device on wheels. The software-defined vehicle has several advantages compared to its hardware-defined predecessor, including the ability to receive over-the-air updates that cover security patches, infotainment improvements, and monitoring and tuning of core functional capabilities of the vehicle, such as powertrain and vehicle dynamics. The software-defined vehicle is expected to play a key role in the future of the automotive industry, as consumers increasingly look for features defined by software, such as driver assistance features, infotainment innovations, and intelligent connectivity solutions. Such an approach will create a strong link with the infrastructure and the need for edge services for the cars will exponentially increase.

The European Union has set a long-term goal of moving as close as possible to zero fatalities in road transport by 2050 [61]. This ambitious target is part of the EU's Road Safety Policy Framework 2021-2030, which aims to reduce the number of road deaths and serious injuries in the EU. The EU is committed to achieving this goal through various measures, such as improving road infrastructure (also thanks to sensors and V2X communications), promoting safer vehicles (again using V2X and ADAS technologies), and raising awareness about road safety.

- **Challenges**

The primary adverse factor influencing CCAM services at the edge is the limited availability of commercial edge servers within mobile networks. The deployment of CCAM solutions cannot be assured in an environment that can consistently deliver network performance in line with the capabilities offered by edge servers. This scarcity of availability also constrains CCAM service developers, hindering their ability to invest in the development of CCAM services tailored for edge computing.

This constraint is further exacerbated by the current scarcity of CVs, resulting in a relatively small market size. The limited number of CVs on the roads significantly impacts the CCAM services at the edge market.

Moreover, the absence of standardized procedures for C-ITS message communication on mobile networks constitutes another detrimental factor. CCAM edge services are primarily designed for critical and safety-related applications, leveraging edge computing's low-latency advantages. The absence of standardized communication procedures poses challenges for CCAM service providers, as it hampers their ability to offer services that can be widely adopted without encountering interoperability issues.

In essence, the confluence of limited commercial edge server presence, a small market size due to the scarcity of CVs, and the absence of standardized communication procedures on mobile networks collectively act as significant impediments to the growth and development of CCAM services at the edge.

Competitive landscape

Despite the widespread excitement surrounding the concept of edge computing, the current commercial services are predominantly tailored towards verticals such as "Industry 4.0." While this

trend prevails, notable interest in the CCAM market is evident among Network Operators, OEMs, as well as emerging players like start-ups, SMEs, and over-the-top (OTT) entities.

Major players in the edge computing market include IBM Corporation (U.S.), Intel Corporation (U.S.), com, Inc. (U.S.), Google LLC (U.S.), Microsoft Corporation (U.S.), ADLINK Technology Inc. (Taiwan), Hewlett Packard Enterprise Development LP (U.S.), Cisco Systems, Inc. (U.S.), Huawei Technologies Co., Ltd. (U.S.), EdgeConneX Inc. (U.S.).

Commercial applications to be used within the Intel Smart Edge environment are promoted at [62]. Several applications are offered and some of them, even if not explicitly developed for CCAM, can be exploited also for the CCAM context. Other initiative related to CCAM the others Horizon Europe project. A marketplace of applications is available at [63]. Some of these applications are related to the automotive vertical and they are devised to be run on edge servers.

Comparison between the PODIUM approach and the competition

The edge computing market is currently still searching for profitable services that can justify the investment and maintenance costs of the infrastructure needed to provide low latency and scalability. The automotive sector is surely one of the most interesting market and PODIUM is experimenting real-services with a high TRL level exploiting demonstration sites equipped with sensors providing a near-to-the-market approach and the possibility to develop quite mature solutions.

Using the edge of the network in CCAM services in PODIUM gives an advantage of consolidating geographically-distributed RUs, so inherits the edge computing advantages of processing and latency that other mobile services offer.

Conclusion:

The landscape of CCAM services at the edge reflects a convergence of technological advancements, increasing CV penetration, supportive regulatory frameworks, and strategic collaborations, which collectively shape a promising market forecast. As the market matures, interconnected technologies evolve, and synergies between CVs, V2X technology, and edge computing strengthen, the trajectory of CCAM services at the edge appears optimistic. With projections pointing towards robust growth, the market is poised for expansion, unlocking new opportunities and paving the way for transformative developments in connected and cooperative automated mobility. As these factors align, the stage is set for an era of innovation, where CCAM services at the edge play a pivotal role in reshaping the future of transportation towards safer, more efficient, and sustainable mobility solutions.

3. PoDIUM ecosystem

The CCAM represents a transformative paradigm in the realm of transportation, promising to revolutionize the way people and goods move within and between urban areas. CCAM integrates cutting-edge technologies such as AVs, connectivity, and cooperative systems to create a seamless and efficient mobility network. In this narrative, the key components, benefits and challenges of the CCAM are analysed as follows.

Components of CCAM

1. **Autonomous Vehicles:** AVs are at the core of the CCAM. These vehicles leverage advanced sensors, machine learning algorithms, and artificial intelligence to navigate and make decisions without human intervention. The integration of AVs into the ecosystem aims to enhance safety, reduce traffic congestion, and optimize transportation efficiency.
2. **Connectivity:** The connectivity aspect of CCAM involves the intercommunication between vehicles, infrastructure, and other elements of the transportation network. Through V2X communication, vehicles share real-time data about their position, speed, and other relevant information, enabling them to make informed decisions and coordinate with each other.
3. **Cooperative systems:** Cooperative systems refer to the collaboration between different entities within the mobility ecosystem. This includes V2V communication, where vehicles share information to enhance safety, and V2I communication, which allows vehicles to interact with traffic signals, road signs, and other infrastructure components.

Benefits of CCAM:

- **Improved safety:** The integration of autonomous technology and cooperative systems has the potential to significantly reduce accidents caused by human error. Vehicles can communicate and respond to potential hazards in real-time, enhancing overall road safety.
- **Efficient traffic flow:** CCAM aims to optimize traffic flow by reducing congestion through coordinated movements of AVs. Intelligent algorithms can manage traffic in real-time, adjusting routes and speeds to minimize delays.
- **Environmental sustainability:** The use of CAVs allows for more efficient transportation routes, leading to reduced fuel consumption and lower emissions. This contributes to environmental sustainability and aligns with global efforts to mitigate climate change.

Challenges:

- **Cybersecurity risks:** The reliance on connectivity introduces cybersecurity concerns. Hacking or malicious interference could compromise the safety and functionality of AVs, requiring robust cybersecurity measures to protect the entire ecosystem.
- **Infrastructure integration:** The successful implementation of CCAM necessitates significant upgrades to existing infrastructure. This includes the installation of smart traffic signals, road sensors, and other components that support seamless communication between vehicles and the environment.
- **Regulatory framework:** Developing a comprehensive and standardized regulatory framework is crucial for the widespread adoption of CCAM. Governments and regulatory bodies must establish guidelines to ensure the safety, privacy, and ethical use of autonomous and connected technologies.

PoDIUM comprehensively understands the components and challenges of CCAM mainly with a primary focus on infrastructure-related issues. Similar to the majority of V2X UCs, the importance of Edge Computing in PoDIUM cannot be overstated. This is especially crucial as many cases ultimately necessitate assurances of low latency and high reliability. These cases entail a substantial volume of regional data that requires local processing and dispatching, rather than being sent over the Internet to cloud services. Scaling this process can become time- and cost-intensive without yielding substantial added value.

In general, PoDIUM asserts that current communication network architectures and cloud computing deployments in existing PDI systems are not fully optimized to effectively meet the evolving requirements of CAVs. In response, PoDIUM proposes an extended use of connectivity and cooperation enablers based on locally generated and distributed computed data. This approach aims to establish trust and sustainability concepts to address these challenges, coupled with a proposed system architecture capable of handling the anticipated surge in data traffic from CAVs.

It is thus evident that stakeholders within the PoDIUM ecosystem, such as vehicle manufacturers, technology solution vendors, road operators, network operators and service providers, must collaborate to establish a platform architecture capable of supporting a diverse range of Vehicle-to-Cloud (V2Cloud) services. It is crucial to consider that the global distribution of vehicle fleets, vehicle data communications, and the processing of such data at scale pose significant challenges to currently deployed architectures.

This section outlines the relationships and interactions among various roles within the PoDIUM ecosystem. This initial step is crucial for gaining a comprehensive understanding of the ecosystem and its characteristics. It will prove instrumental in exploring associated business models concerning the PoDIUM platform in the subsequent phases of the project.

Initially, the various roles of actors participating in the ecosystem are presented. The section concludes by presenting the initial reference model for the PoDIUM platform. The following definitions are used in the following sections:

- **Actor:** an entity that participates in the business model, it can provide or consume services.
- **Role:** the functionality of each actor that participates in the business model. An actor can take one or more of the roles, while a role can be undertaken by several actors.
- **Relationship:** the interaction between two roles in the model.

3.1. Actors and Roles

In this new era, CCAM involves a number of actors/roles cross-collaborating in the value chain. These actors/roles include not only traditional roles like vehicle manufacturers and road infrastructure operators but also actors/roles from other industries – ICT etc.

Many actors/players are entering the market following different approaches, either collaborating or competing with traditional actors/players. Given the rapid growth of CCAM, these actors/players are actively positioning themselves in the value chain, assessing all opportunities to deliver enhanced value and maximize profit potential.

Considering PoDIUM architecture and UCs, the PoDIUM platform assumes a central role in the ecosystem, adopting the proposed solutions and tools. The subsequent paragraphs describe the key actors and roles in this dynamic landscape.

Table 5: Actors/Roles of PoDIUM ecosystem

Actor / Role	Description	Example
Fixed and Mobile Network Operators (MNO) ¹⁹	The success of PoDIUM and in general of CCAM heavily relies on seamless communication between vehicles, infrastructure, and other elements of the ecosystem. Telecommunication providers play a vital role in deploying and providing the necessary connectivity infrastructure, including 5G networks, to support real-time communication and data exchange among vehicles and with the surrounding environment. They own the physical equipment such as fiber, base stations, antennas, switches, etc.	Orange, Deutsche Telekom, Telefonica, Verizon, AT&T etc.
Cloud Infrastructure Providers	They provide the required storage, cloud computing and corresponding networking resources (CPUs, RAM, storage). These can be in a central cloud location or locally deployed in edge servers.	Amazon Web Services (AWS), Microsoft Azure, Google Cloud, Alibaba Cloud, IBM Cloud, Oracle, Salesforce, SAP, Rackspace Cloud, VMWare
Road Infrastructure operators	They are responsible for the deployment, operation, and maintenance of the road infrastructure. They can also own and operate road-side facilities such as ICT equipment, cameras and sensors located in the road networks	Government transportation agencies such as the Department of Transportation in the USA, Transport for London (TfL) in the UK, and the Roads and Transport Authority (RTA) in Dubai.
Traffic Management Center (TMC) operators	They oversee the real-time monitoring and control of traffic flow. TMC operators play a central role in optimizing road network efficiency, ensuring safety, and supporting the integration of AVs. They are responsible for managing intelligent traffic management systems, coordinating responses to incidents, and facilitating communication	Regional transportation agencies, city TMCs, and private entities specializing in traffic control and monitoring, such as Siemens Mobility, Kapsch TrafficCom, and Iteris. This role can also

¹⁹ Neutral Host, like Cellnex, American Tower, and similar entities, can also be included in this category. These organizations own and manage essential physical telecom infrastructure—such as fiber cables, base stations, antennas, and switches—that is crucial for enabling advanced CCAM applications.

Actor / Role	Description	Example
	between vehicles and infrastructure. These operators utilize advanced technologies and data analytics to make informed decisions, adapt traffic signal timings, and implement dynamic strategies to minimize congestion.	be played by road infrastructure operators.
HW Vendors	They provide all types of hardware to all interested parties, for example, base stations, antennas, switches, routers, servers, network cards, sensors, cameras, CPUs, RAM, RSUs, entertainment systems, etc.	Huawei, Cisco, Ericsson, Nokia, NVIDIA, Bosch, HP, Dell, Accelleran, ADVA, Athonet,
SW Providers	They provide all the necessary generic software that is required by all parties. For example, the firmware that is required for the hardware devices and the platforms, etc. This role does not include the development and provision of CAV & 3 rd parties services and apps.	Microsoft or Linux Foundation, APEX AI, eclipse foundation
CAV & 3 rd parties services and apps developers/providers	They develop and/or provide CAV & 3 rd parties services and apps to vehicle manufacturers.	Bosch, Waymo, Aurora Innovation, Aptiv, Mobileye (Intel), Cruise (GM Cruise) owned by General Motors, Baidu Apollo, NVIDIA, TomTom, AutonomouStuff (Acquired by Hexagon), Renovo
Service Providers	They are responsible for creating advanced services, e.g., using/packaging PoDIUM services, and providing them to end users and or vehicle manufacturers	SME's and or SW houses
Vehicle Manufacturers	They are developing and deploying (autonomous) vehicles. Such companies invest heavily in research and development to create advanced autonomous driving systems. These entities are crucial in shaping the technological landscape of PoDIUM and CCAM in general.	Tesla, Waymo, and traditional automakers such as BMW, Ford, and General Motors, Stellantis etc.
End Users	All types of users who are the recipients of the provided services. They can be individual users (Business-to-Customer (B2C)) or business customers (Business-to-Business (B2B)).	Vehicle owners, drivers, passengers or pedestrians, freight and logistics, or providers of public services.

3.2. Incentives/benefits for the different roles to use/participate in the platform

This section discusses the anticipated developments and benefits in the different actors/roles of the ecosystem stemming from the introduction of the PoDIUM platform.

3.2.1. Infrastructure providers: Network operators and cloud providers

Infrastructure providers are expected to gain significant benefits as enablers of CCAM. Engagement with the PoDIUM platform can assist Infrastructure Providers in discerning emerging market and business challenges, recognizing potential opportunities, and promptly identifying novel business models. Furthermore, this interaction enables Infrastructure Providers to venture into the lucrative automotive market and expand their portfolio of applications and services. For example, by combining cellular communications with short-range ad-hoc communications, MNOs can expand their 5G networks to offer C-ITS services. This extension enables seamless connectivity to vehicles, facilitating the exchange of crucial information. In addition, both MNOs and Cloud Infrastructure Providers can experience an increase in the consumption of their edge and cloud services due to the need for local data processing and decision making.

3.2.2. Road operators/TMC operators

Road operators and TMC operators stand to gain valuable insights from the data shared by CVs, enabling the implementation of innovative strategies and tactics for effective traffic management. The ability to interact with CAVs and VRUs empowers road operators to regulate demand by establishing guidelines for vehicle behavior. In PoDIUM, the road operator receives mobility data from both RUs and sensors, allowing the implementation of optimal traffic management strategies. This optimization not only enhances CCAM services, including emergency services, but also improves overall traffic flow and road capacity.

Moreover, the utilization of their infrastructure during the UCs provides them with valuable insights into necessary upgrades. This may include the introduction of new equipment with enhanced capabilities. Collaborating with big players in the industry becomes crucial, as they can articulate their expectations and requirements for future automotive applications, guiding the creation of innovative solutions.

3.2.3. HW vendors

Providers of equipment closely monitor the relevant markets and their evolving trends. While many technical features adhere to 3GPP and other standards, vendors concentrate their product development efforts on features that exhibit a growing and stable future demand, ensuring a reliable revenue stream. The automotive industry's robust demand for products like the PoDIUM platform serves as a compelling indicator for vendors to align their development strategies accordingly.

Deploying equipment during UCs aids in validating products in new applications and services, enabling the identification of areas for future improvement to meet evolving requirements. An additional benefit lies in the increased knowledge gained in advanced techniques and technologies. This engagement provides valuable insights into incorporating these sophisticated features into upcoming products.

3.2.4. SW providers and CAV & 3rd parties services and apps developers/providers

The open development principles adopted during the design and development of the PoDIUM platform, the availability of a high volume of data from different sources as well as the need to combine different wireless communication systems allows SW Vendors and CAV & 3rd parties services and apps developers/providers to develop advanced SW pieces as well as services and applications. These factors also contribute to the establishment and growth of dedicated software development teams, specifically focused on crafting platform solutions, expansions, and interfaces.

3.2.5. Service providers

Service Providers are expected to benefit from PoDIUM platform by mainly expanding their service portfolio. Service Providers will be able to create and provide advanced PoDIUM services and applications to End Users and Vehicle Manufacturers using or packaging PoDIUM services.

In addition, service providers are expected to expand their services by treating data from various sources and making it easily accessible to others. This may involve providing information through C-ITS services to vehicles, VRUs, and other interfaces, facilitating interoperability and coordination between different entities.

3.2.6. Vehicle manufacturers

The automotive industry is expected to enhance the capabilities of connected and automated vehicles to meet the evolving needs of urban and highway mobility. New strategies for data generation and sharing will be developed, enabling vehicles to share information. This could involve reacting to cooperative manoeuvres, responding to EVs, and interacting with VRUs. Vehicles will incorporate new functionalities to improve road safety and traffic efficiency. These functionalities may include cooperative manoeuvres and responsiveness to emergencies, contributing to a reduction in environmental impact. Furthermore, active involvement in PoDIUM UCs empowers them to comprehend the essential requirements for deploying novel services. This understanding enables the adaptation of both hardware and software in their vehicles, ensuring preparedness for the market entry of these applications."

3.2.7. End Users

End Users are expected to gain significant benefits from the introduction of the PoDIUM platform in terms of safety, environment and economy. In detail, the following benefits are anticipated:

- **Enhanced safety:** PoDIUM is poised to increase safety by providing real-time notifications of emergencies on the road, such as accident or traffic jam alerts. By facilitating the sharing and synchronization of maneuvers, PoDIUM contributes to heightened safety measures.
- **Improved emergency services:** Sharing information about critical incidents like accidents or traffic jams enables prompt access for public authorities, thereby enhancing the effectiveness of emergency services. This is particularly crucial in high-risk areas like highway tunnels, supporting medical assistance, disaster recovery, and safety services.
- **Enhanced traffic flow:** PoDIUM will enhance traffic flow by delivering real-time traffic data to CAVs and other vehicles. This data empowers vehicles to choose alternative paths based on accurate information, ultimately increasing road utilization and optimizing traffic conditions.

- **Emissions reduction:** PoDIUM will reduce emissions by shortening the time-to-destination for each driver. The provision of accurate and real-time traffic information is anticipated to increase road utilization, leading to a corresponding reduction in estimated time-to-destination.
- **Improved VRU detection:** PoDIUM will increase the detection rate of VRUs and enable direct communication between the TMC and VRUs, minimizing potential hazardous situations, particularly in busy crossroads.

3.3. PoDIUM reference model

The next phase involves delineating the relationships among stakeholders in the PoDIUM environment. The associated reference model encompasses a diverse array of actors/roles and a complex value network. Figure 7 illustrates PoDIUM reference model, outlining all participating actors/roles, relationship interfaces, and revenue streams.

Definitions:

- The direction of arrows in the model signifies the flow of services.
- Revenue flow is considered to move in the opposite direction. In certain instances, there is bidirectional revenue sharing between two roles.
- The rectangle with a dotted line symbolizes an actor and an actor may assume one or more roles. The rectangular boxes within the dotted-line rectangles depict these roles.

It is important to acknowledge that there are additional relationships between the roles, such as hardware (HW) vendors supplying equipment to all other members of the ecosystem. However, these relationships are not explored, as they do not impact the business model of the PoDIUM platform provider.

Figure 7: PoDIUM Reference Model

The business relationships within the reference model are outlined as follows:

- **HW equipment:**
 - **Description:** Represents the relationship between actors for the provisioning of ICT-related equipment.
 - **Participants:** HW vendor provides hardware equipment to infrastructure providers and the PoDIUM platform.
- **SW:**
 - **Description:** Represents the relationship between actors for the provisioning of software.
 - **Participants:** SW providers deliver SW to the HW vendors, infrastructure providers, and the PoDIUM platform.
- **ICT resources:**
 - **Description:** A broad term encompassing various resources (connectivity, computational resources, RSU, etc.) provided by infrastructure providers.
 - **Participants:** Involves the fixed network operators, MNOs and the Cloud Infrastructure Providers
- **Resources (Vehicles):**
 - **Description:** Represents the relationship between actors for the provisioning of vehicles provided by the vehicle manufacturer to end users.
 - **Participants:** Vehicle manufacturers provide vehicles to end users
- **CAV & 3rd parties services and apps:**
 - **Description:** Represents the relationship between actors for the provisioning of CAV & 3rd parties services and apps including infotainment apps, automation-related services etc.
 - **Participants:** CAV & 3rd parties services and apps developers/providers provide such services and apps to vehicle manufacturers
- **PoDIUM Services:**
 - **Description:** Represents the portfolio of services provided by the PoDIUM platform.
 - **Participants:** Involves service providers, vehicle manufacturers and end users.

It should be highlighted that this is a first, general reference model including all possible actors/roles and their interactions. For example, we assume that the road infrastructure operator and Traffic Management Center Operator are two different roles. However, these roles can be merged into one actor/role. In addition, a Service Provider is also included assuming that this actor will be able to create and provide advanced services by using or packaging PoDIUM's services. This reference model will be refined and finalized in Task 6.2 and documented in D6.2 upon the definition of the business model to be adopted/followed.

The business model(s) to be adopted/followed is of paramount importance since this will also define the PoDIUM's service delivery method. As shown in the general reference model of Figure 7, there are several options to deliver PoDIUM's services. PoDIUM services can be delivered directly to end users from PoDIUM platform. Moreover, PoDIUM services can also be delivered to vehicle manufacturers and the latter to provide them to end users.

Another viable option is to position the service provider as an intermediary between the PoDIUM platform and end users as well as vehicle manufacturers. As mentioned above, the Service Provider may be able to use or package PoDIUM's services to create and provide advanced services. Thus, these

advanced services can then be delivered to end users either directly or indirectly through vehicle manufacturers.

It is interesting to note that the success of any CCAM platform in general and of the PoDIUM platform in particular is based on the availability and exchange of a high volume of data. This is also illustrated in the reference model of Figure 7. PoDIUM platform is exchanging data with the road infrastructure operator, TMC operator and/or CAV & 3rd parties services and apps developers/providers. In addition, the road infrastructure operator exchanges data with TMC operator. On the other hand, end users are providing data to PoDIUM platform, TMC operator and/or road infrastructure operator facilitating the decision making, traffic management and optimization as well as other processes and functionalities of the involved roles.

4. Factors affecting the success of PoDIUM

This section aims to assess the various challenges that are related to the successful adoption of PoDIUM solutions. In order to identify the barriers and drivers of the uptake of PoDIUM an expert survey was conducted to rate the different criteria that are expected to be relevant to its success. To assess the relative importance of these criteria, the AHP method was selected as the most appropriate. A set of criteria and their corresponding sub-criteria were selected and an online survey was implemented. Experts from the PoDIUM project were invited to express their opinions regarding the factors that will mostly influence the future of the PoDIUM solution. The responses collected and processed to derive the final results.

4.1. Decision making using the AHP framework

In this sub-section, the methodology used to identify the factors affecting PoDIUM market adoption and evolution is initially presented. The hierarchy along with the identified factors and sub-factors are provided and explained. The questionnaire drafted to conduct the survey is then described. Finally, the results derived from the implementation of the AHP methodology are discussed.

4.1.1. Methodology

AHP was proposed and developed by Thomas Saaty [67] in the early 1970s mainly for military purposes. The AHP is a multi-criteria decision-making approach. In the past, AHP was extensively used covering several application areas such as education [68], engineering [69], industry [70], manufacturing [71] and resource allocation [72]. Recently, AHP was widely used for selecting and ranking alternatives in the field of ICT [73]–[76].

AHP is a structured technique for dealing with complex decisions. It describes a rational and comprehensive framework for decomposing an unstructured complex problem into a multi-level hierarchy of interrelated criteria, sub-criteria and decision alternatives. By incorporating judgments on qualitative and quantitative criteria, AHP manages to quantify decision makers' preferences. The priorities of criteria, sub-criteria and alternatives are finally reached by combining these judgments.

Figure 8: Analytic Hierarchy Process steps

Figure 8 illustrates the required steps of AHP. In the first step, the problem that is investigated is formed while criteria and sub-criteria contributing to objective’s satisfaction are determined through interviews and/or group discussions with experts. The multi-level hierarchy is then constructed (Figure 9) consisting of three levels. In the first level, the objective under investigation is shown. In this work, the factors affecting the adoption and evolution of PoDIUM and its proposed solution in general is examined. In the next level, the criteria, Cr_k with $k=1,2,\dots,N$ and N the total number of criteria, participating in the decision-making process are determined. Criteria should be general enough, incorporating several features resulting in a rough description of the objective. In the lower level, criteria are further analysed into their sub-criteria SC_{ijk} , where $j=1,2,\dots,M_k$ and M_k is the number of sub-criteria under criterion k . Sub-criteria represent a specific feature characterizing a criterion. Identification of criteria and sub-criteria is accomplished based on the focus of their preferential independence.

Figure 9: Multi-level hierarchy of interrelated criteria and sub-criteria

Once the hierarchical structure is constructed and criteria and sub-criteria are determined, appropriate questionnaires are conducted and distributed to experts (step 2). This procedure is based on pairwise judgments of experts from the second to the lowest level of the hierarchy. In each level, the criteria (sub-criteria) are compared pairwise according to their degree of influence and based on the specified criteria in the higher level. The described comparisons are performed using the standardized nine-level scale shown in Table 6.

Table 6: The Saaty Rating Scale

Intensity of importance	Definition	Explanation
1	Equal importance	The two criteria contribute equally
3	Moderate importance	Experience and judgment favour one of the criteria
5	Strong importance	A criterion is strongly favoured
7	Very strong importance	A criterion is very strong dominant
9	Extreme importance	A criterion is favoured by at least an order of magnitude
2, 4, 6, 8	Intermediate values	Used to compromise between two of the above numbers

The set of pairwise comparisons on the N criteria results in an $N \times N$ evaluation matrix $A=[A_{ij}]$ in which the elements A_{ij} (>0) represent the relative importance of criterion Cr_i compared to Cr_j . It should be noted that $A_{ii}=1$ for every i while matrix A is symmetrical across the main diagonal that is $A_{ji}=1/A_{ij}$. The

same steps are followed regarding sub-criteria of each criterion k and the results are summarized in a similar to A matrix called A_k .

The last step (step 3) towards the evaluation of the objectives is the estimation of criteria and sub-criteria weights, w_k and s_{jk} respectively. This requires the calculation of the principal eigenvector $\mathbf{v}=[v_k]$ (or $\mathbf{u}_k=[u_{ik}]$) that is the eigenvector corresponding to the maximum eigenvalue λ_{\max} (principal eigenvalue) of matrix \mathbf{A} (or \mathbf{A}_k). The weights of criterion k and its sub-criterion j are given by:

$$w_k = \frac{v_k}{\sum_{i=1}^N v_i} \tag{1}$$

$$s_{jk} = \frac{u_{jk}}{\sum_{i=1}^{M_k} u_{ik}} \tag{2}$$

where N and M_k is the number of criteria and sub-criteria of criterion k respectively.

4.1.2. Consistency of pairwise comparison matrices

In order to maintain a certain quality level of a decision, the consistency of the data should also be investigated during the analysis. It should be noted that the rank of matrix A (or A_k) equals 1 and $\lambda_{\max}=N$ (or M_k) if the pairwise comparisons are completely consistent. In this case, weights can be estimated by normalizing any of the columns or rows of A (A_k). A consistency index (CI) was introduced by Saaty in 1977 [67]:

$$CI = \frac{\lambda_{\max} - N}{N - 1} \tag{3}$$

where λ_{\max} is the largest (maximum) eigenvalue and N is the number of criteria. The final consistency ratio (CR), showing how consistent the judgments have been relative to large samples of purely random judgments, is given by:

$$CR = \frac{CI}{RI} \tag{4}$$

where RI is the random index calculated as the average CI across a large number of randomly filled matrices using the scale described earlier in this section. The random indices for several values of N were calculated by Saaty in 2003 [77] and are given in Table 7. The consistency ratio should be less than 0.1. A CR larger than the tolerable level of 0.1 demonstrates the need to exclude the pairwise comparison matrix of this respondent for further analysis so as not to affect the overall accuracy of the results.

Table 7: RI values for different values of n

n	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
RI	0	0	0.58	0.90	1.12	1.24	1.32	1.41	1.45

4.2. Determining the set of criteria and factors to be used in the surveys

In order to identify the factors that influence the adoption of PoDIUM solutions, a survey was designed in WP6 in line with the AHP methodology. For this purpose, the following set of criteria covering a wide range of factors were initially defined:

- Basic PoDIUM features for enhanced system performance / capabilities
- CCAM Service Management Add-on features

- Business and Strategy
- Acceptance / Flexibility

Each of these criteria was further broken down into sub-criteria which are usually indicative attributes that can be quantified and are closely related to the criteria. A brief description of the criteria and their sub-criteria is shown in Table 8.

Table 8: Description of criteria and sub-criteria

(sub-)Criterion	Explanation
Cr1: Basic PoDIUM features for enhanced system performance / capabilities	Aspects associated with the performance/quality of service of PoDIUM such as low latency, reliability etc.
SCr1.1: Near real-time communications (Low latency)	<10ms latency between the transmission of a message from a transmitter and the successful reception of the message at the receiver
SCr1.2: Reliable Communications	Ensure that data connectivity is constantly available and data are properly transferred i.e., transmitted complete and uncorrupted to the intended recipient
SCr1.3: Support heterogeneity of road users and comm channels	The ability of the system to support different kinds of RUs (e.g. CAVs and VRUs) and their respective communication channels.
SCr1.4: Trustworthiness of messages (authenticity and integrity)	Ensure that a message has not been tampered with or altered by malicious actions and that it comes from a trusted source. Take into account the reliability of the different data sources (Data truthfulness).
Cr2: CCAM Service Management Add-on features	Features of the system that manage the operation of CVs, CAVs and other connected RU, especially VRUs.
SCr2.1: Optimized traffic management	It indicates the optimal traffic management strategies leading to optimized operation, lower congestion, environmental impact etc.
SCr2.2: RU detection and protection	RUs will be detected through Artificial Intelligence devices (cameras) and, potentially, a RU APP. Affected RUs and vehicles are informed to avoid risks.
SCr2.3: Enhanced situational awareness	Ability to identify the surrounding environment and/or “objects” based on the cooperation between systems, vehicles and RUs as well as on a common time-space reference
SCr2.4: Dynamic and cooperative risk assessment	Innovative system that provides accurate and real-time information about the risk level based on the exchange of the needed information between systems, CVs, CAVs and VRUs.
SCr2.5: Dynamic and cooperative planner	A system capable of solving in real-time sophisticated traffic situations with blockages and

(sub-)Criterion	Explanation
	occlusions based on the exchange of the needed information between systems, CVs, CAVs and VRUs.
Cr3: Business and Strategy	Aspects related to the business perspectives such as new market opportunities, cost and new business model
SCr3.1: Cost	Induced Costs related to hardware, software, installation and maintenance
SCr3.2: Compliance to Standards and Specifications	The system must follow requirements imposed by the standardization bodies and fora. In addition, the system meets the listed acceptance criteria. It also includes compatibility of Equipment with legacy systems.
SCr3.3: New business models	New players entering the market and traditional roles will be changed. Advanced applications/services will emerge changing the current revenue streams
SCr3.4: Market growth opportunities	New value propositions. Advanced CCAM solutions can be a means of market growth
Cr4: Acceptance / Flexibility	It refers to the overall usability of the system and incorporates many user-related concerns
SCr4.1: Security and Privacy	Share sensitive information of CVs in a secure way, while ensuring compliance with data protection regulations.
SCr4.2: Regulatory issues	Regulation issues include information exchange, traffic management policies, emergency services as well as directives setting out minimum safety requirements for tunnels on TEN-T
SCr4.3: Scalability	Ability of the system to continue functioning properly when changed in size or volume

The full list of the criteria and their sub-criteria is illustrated in the hierarchy of Figure 10.

Figure 10: PoDIUM hierarchy

4.2.1. Survey description

The survey was implemented in the form of an online set of questions created using LimeSurvey (<https://www.limesurvey.org/>), an open-source tool for web surveys, and hosted at: <https://incites.eu/PODIUM/index.php/343784>.

An introductory page provides information on the project and the AHP methodology as portrayed indicatively in the following figures.

PoDiUM market adoption survey

This is a survey conducted by the PoDiUM H2020 project with the objective to identify the factors that can affect the market adoption of PoDiUM. The responses are anonymous, the aggregated data will be used in the upcoming deliverable D6.1: Market and actor-role analysis of PoDiUM.

In the following figure, the hierarchy used in the analysis is shown. In the first level, the objective under investigation is shown, which consists of the factors affecting the adoption and evolution of the PoDiUM solution. In the next level, the criteria affecting the objective are determined. The criteria are general enough to incorporate several features resulting in a rough description of the objective. In the next level, the criteria are further analyzed into their sub-criteria. Sub-criteria represent a specific feature characterizing a criterion.

You can download the list of criteria and subcriteria and their definition using the following link

PoDiUM will identify and assess the connectivity and cooperation enablers to reach higher levels of automation and advance important Physical and Digital Infrastructure (PDI) technologies, through a multi-connectivity approach and an interoperable and hybrid data management environment. You can learn more about the project on the website and follow us on the social media:

Twitter: @PoDiUM_EU
 LinkedIn: PoDiUM Project

PoDiUM has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101069547.

Co-funded by the European Union

Figure 11: PoDiUM survey introductory page

The following Figure depicts an example of the AHP question implementation in the survey. The necessary calculations were performed using Matlab, leading to an estimation of the weights signifying the importance of criteria and sub-criteria. The responses were strictly anonymous. A brief info sheet was presented to inform responders about the purpose of the survey. In addition, a downloadable file containing detailed descriptions of the criteria and sub-criteria has been incorporated for further reference. Participants in the survey can access this document to gain a comprehensive understanding of the analytical framework used in assessing PoDiUM solutions.

PoDIUM
Resume later

16%

Comparison of Criteria

PoDIUM project has identified the following four criteria as the most important:

- **C1: Basic PoDIUM features for enhanced system performance/capabilities:** PoDIUM features that enhance performance/quality of service in terms of, e.g., low latency, reliability, security etc.
- **C2: CCAM Service Management Add-on Features:** Service-level features of the system that manage the operation of Connected Vehicles (CVs), CAVs and other connected road users, especially VRUs.
- **C3: Business and Strategy:** Aspects related to the business perspectives such as new market opportunities, cost and new business model
- **C4: Acceptance / Flexibility:** It refers to the overall usability of the system and incorporates many user-related concerns

Please answer the questions using the following instructions:

Each criterion will be rated according to its degree of relative importance to the other criteria within the group using pair wise comparisons to rank them. Please indicate your preference between two criteria by providing your preference between 1 and 9.

When two criteria are of equal importance, they should take a score of 1. When one criterion is more important than another criterion, then it should take a score between 2 and 9, depending on how much more important it is compared to the other criterion, with 9 indicating that is much more important.

Please indicate your preference between two criteria by providing your preference between 1 and 9

Number	Scale
9	Extremely preferred
8	Very strong to extremely preferred
7	Very strong preferred
6	Strongly to very strongly preferred
5	Strongly preferred
4	Moderately to strongly preferred
3	Moderately preferred
2	Equally to moderately preferred
1	Equally preferred

Which of the following do you consider more important?

C1: Basic PoDIUM features for enhanced system performance / capabilities

C2: CCAM Service Management Add-on features

Figure 12: Example of AHP questions

The survey had a total of 33 questions some of which were not AHP based. Table 9 presents an analysis of the number of questions in terms of criteria and sub-criteria.

Table 9: Analysis of the number of questions

Type	Description	Number	Number of questions
Criteria	Criteria that will affect PoDIUM	4	6
Sub-criteria	Related to Basic PoDIUM features for enhanced system performance / capabilities criterion	4	6
Sub-criteria	Related to CCAM Service Management Add-on features criterion	5	10
Sub-criteria	Related to Business and Strategy criterion	4	6
Sub-criteria	Related to Acceptance / Flexibility criterion	3	3
Demographic	Type of organization and Position	2	2

At the beginning of the survey two questions were posed about the type of organisation and the position of the participants. The following figures illustrate the statistics of the participants.

Figure 13: Statistics of the participants

4.2.2. Results and discussion

In this section, we present and discuss the results of the survey concerning the evaluation of the importance of the criteria and sub-criteria that are expected to affect the market adoption of PoDIUM solutions. From the thirty-eight experts who initially participated in the survey, fifteen questionnaires were discarded as inconsistent, since their associated CR was >0.1 . The questionnaires were conducted and completed during a period of 1 month. This can be assumed a sufficient size for an AHP analysis since as shown in [78], [79], the changes in the probability of rank reversal when an additional expert is added to the group are below 1% at $M = 15$ (where M is the number of experts). Using the methodology described above, one can easily estimate the weights prioritizing the criteria and sub-criteria (Table 10).

Table 10: Weights prioritizing the criteria and sub-criteria

Criteria / Sub-criteria	Weight
C₁: Basic PoDIUM features for enhanced system performance / capabilities	0,38
SC ₁₁ : Near real-time communications (Low latency)	0,174
SC ₁₂ : Reliable Communications	0,292
SC ₁₃ : Support heterogeneity of road users and comm channels	0,199
SC ₁₄ : Trustworthiness of messages (authenticity and integrity)	0,337
C₂: CCAM Service Management Add-on features	0,27
SC ₂₁ : Optimized traffic management	0,15
SC ₂₂ : RU detection and protection	0,293
SC ₂₃ : Enhanced situational awareness	0,233
SC ₂₄ : Dynamic and cooperative risk assessment	0,179
SC ₂₅ : Dynamic and cooperative planner	0,148
C₃: Business and Strategy	0,17
SC ₃₁ : Cost	0,27

Criteria / Sub-criteria	Weight
SC ₃₂ : Compliance to Standards and Specifications	0,298
SC ₃₃ : New business models	0,189
SC ₃₄ : Market Growth Opportunities	0,245
C₄: Acceptance / Flexibility	0,19
SC ₄₁ : Security and Privacy	0,493
SC ₄₂ : Regulatory issues	0,239
SC ₄₃ : Scalability	0,269

4.2.3. Weighting of criteria

The results concerning the weights of the criteria that are expected to affect PoDIUM penetration are shown in the following figure. According to experts’ opinions, the criterion of 'Basic PoDIUM features for enhanced system performance/capabilities' was ranked as the most crucial. This outcome aligns with expectations, as this criterion primarily addresses security, reliability, and the trustworthiness of messages. These aspects are essential to prevent errors and interventions in the exchanged messages, thereby ensuring the safety of passengers and RUs. The 'CCAM Service Management Add-on Features' criterion holds the second position, underscoring its high importance in delivering advanced functionalities to Cooperative, Connected, and Automated Mobility (CCAM) systems. This placement emphasizes the significance of these additional features in enhancing the overall performance and capabilities of CCAM systems. It is interesting to note that Acceptance and Flexibility as well as Business and Strategy criteria receive the lowest weights although these are relevant to market related issues and aspects that will facilitate the deployment of PoDIUM solutions playing thus a significant role.

Figure 14: Relative weights of criteria

4.2.4. Weighting of sub-criteria under each criterion

It is also interesting to examine the weights of the sub-criteria under each criterion. Regarding Basic PoDIUM features for enhanced system performance / capabilities sub-criterion (Figure 15), the experts seem more concerned about trustworthiness of messages (authenticity and integrity) and reliable communications in view of the many new CCAM applications and services where such requirements are very tight and crucial.

Support heterogeneity of RUs and comm channels sub-criterion is the second most important issue, accumulating a weight of 0.20. Such a factor is also important in both PoDIUM and CCAM. Roads are shared by a variety of RUs, including pedestrians, cyclists, traditional vehicles, and automated vehicles. Such systems must be capable of accommodating and interacting with this diverse mix of participants, each with their unique characteristics and behaviors. Moreover, an effective CCAM system should be able to adapt to the different levels of automation, communication capabilities, and behavior patterns exhibited by different RUs. This adaptability enhances safety and improves traffic flow efficiency. In parallel, such systems need to support interoperability between the different communication channels, ensuring seamless communication and cooperation between various entities on the road.

Figure 15: Relative weights of Basic PoDIUM features for enhanced system performance / capabilities Sub-criteria

Low latency can be found in the last position with a weight of 0.17. This is somehow unexpected since low latency is imperative for real-time decision-making and the safety-critical functions of PoDIUM enable vehicles to respond quickly to changing conditions and potential hazards. Low latency facilitates the exchange of information between vehicles and infrastructure for coordinated traffic management. Quick data transmission allows for timely responses to traffic conditions, optimizing traffic flow and reducing congestion. Last but not least, low-latency communication contributes to a smoother and more predictable driving experience for automated vehicles. This is important for passenger comfort and acceptance of autonomous technologies.

Figure 16 shows that RU detection and protection and enhanced situational awareness are ranked first (0.29 and 0.23 respectively) indicating their increased importance. This ranking is fully consistent with the vision of PoDIUM to enable higher levels of cooperation and automation as well as to integrate the VRUs in the overall PDI. The accurate detection of RUs and the implementation of effective protection measures are integral components of PoDIUM, contributing significantly to safety, traffic flow optimization, and the establishment of trust ensuring the overall success and viability of CCAM systems. Enhanced situational awareness is a cornerstone in the development and operation of CCAM systems. It not only enhances the safety of RUs but also aids in efficient traffic management, cooperative maneuvering, and the overall optimization of the transportation network. The ability to

perceive and understand the surrounding environment in real time is essential for the success of connected and cooperative automated mobility.

Figure 16: Relative weights of CCAM Service Management Add-on features Sub-criteria

The significance of the remaining three sub-criteria, namely dynamic and cooperative risk assessment, optimized traffic management, and dynamic and cooperative planner, appears to be roughly equal, with respective weights of 0.18, 0.15, and 0.15. While all these elements are crucial, their priority can vary based on specific objectives and situations. Safety, as exemplified by dynamic and cooperative risk assessment, is usually the highest priority. Nevertheless, optimized traffic management and a dynamic and cooperative planner are mandatory for establishing a smoothly operating and efficient CCAM system. The synergy between these components is essential for unlocking the full potential of CCAM systems.

As shown in Figure 17, Compliance to Standards and Specifications is ranked first choice among the experts with weight 0.298. Compliance with standards and specifications is critical for the successful implementation and adoption of PoDIUM since it ensures interoperability, safety, and reliability as well as getting regulatory approval and building trust among users and other stakeholders.

According to the experts’ opinions, cost is in the second place (weight: 0.27). This is not surprising as the cost of deployment is very important for the adoption of any new system. Affordability plays a crucial role in the widespread acceptance of these systems, influencing both consumers and businesses. Reducing costs can enhance accessibility and drive broader adoption.

Figure 17: Relative weights of Business and Strategy Sub-criteria

At the third place, one can find Market Growth Opportunities sub-criterion with weight 0.245. Identifying and capitalizing on market growth opportunities is essential for the long-term success and sustainability of PoDIUM. The potential for market expansion, meeting evolving consumer needs, and staying competitive in a growing market are crucial for the ongoing development and adoption of PoDIUM.

It is evident that the relative importance of these three sub-criteria depends on PoDIUM’s phase. During the initial stages of market introduction, compliance and safety might take precedence, while in later stages, cost reduction and capitalizing on market growth opportunities could become more prominent. Thus, it evolves over time as the technology matures and the market dynamics change. A balanced approach that considers all three factors is often necessary for the successful adoption and sustainability of PoDIUM.

In the last position, one can find New Business Models sub-criterion. This is somehow strange since new business models are integral to the business and strategy of PoDIUM. They offer avenues for revenue generation, provide a competitive advantage, enable adaptability to market changes, foster collaboration within the ecosystem, and enhance the overall user experience. Ignoring the importance of innovative business models could limit the success and widespread adoption of PoDIUM.

Regarding the sub-criteria of the Acceptance / Flexibility criterion, security and privacy issues are the most important (weight: 0.493). The very high importance of security and privacy in PoDIUM and CCAM systems, in general, is driven by the need to safeguard human lives, protect sensitive data, build user trust, comply with legal requirements, and ensure the reliability of critical transportation infrastructure. Addressing these concerns is integral to the responsible and successful deployment of PoDIUM and CCAM systems.

Figure 18: Relative weights of Acceptance / Flexibility Sub-criteria

Surprisingly enough, scalability and regulatory issues are deemed of secondary importance (0.269, 0.239 respectively) compared to the security and privacy sub-criterion. As the adoption of PoDIUM increases, scalability becomes essential to accommodate a larger number of CVs and users. In addition, the ability to scale ensures that PoDIUM will remain efficient and effective as traffic volumes increase. In general, scalability supports the vision of creating an ecosystem that can seamlessly integrate with existing infrastructure and accommodate future developments.

The low priority of regulatory issues is somehow unexpected and cannot be easily explained. Regulatory issues are highly important in the context of PoDIUM. Regulatory issues are instrumental in providing a legal and ethical framework for the development and deployment of PoDIUM. They address safety, legal compliance, privacy, and ethical considerations, contributing to the responsible and sustainable integration of automated mobility technologies into the broader landscape. The inability to comply with existing national or European regulations and standards related to information exchange, traffic management data privacy, and emergency services could hinder the market adoption of PoDIUM.

4.2.4.1. Global priorities of sub-criteria and Policy Implications

In order to capture a global view of the sub-criteria ranking, the global priorities need to be calculated. The global priorities are obtained by multiplying the local priorities (sub-criteria weights) by their parent’s priority (weight). The global priorities for all the sub-criteria add up once again to 1. Table 11 presents the global weights (in descending order) for all the sub-criteria considered.

Table 11: Global Priorities of sub-criteria

Sub-criteria	Global Priority
SC ₁₄ : Trustworthiness of messages (authenticity and integrity)	0,127
SC ₁₂ : Reliable Communications	0,11
SC ₄₁ : Security and Privacy	0,092
SC ₂₂ : RU detection and protection	0,078
SC ₁₃ : Support heterogeneity of road users and comm channels	0,075
SC ₁₁ : Near real-time communications (Low latency)	0,066
SC ₂₃ : Enhanced situational awareness	0,062
SC ₃₂ : Compliance to Standards and Specifications	0,0504
SC ₄₃ : Scalability	0,0503
SC ₂₄ : Dynamic and cooperative risk assessment	0,048
SC ₃₁ : Cost	0,046
SC ₄₂ : Regulatory issues	0,045
SC ₃₄ : Market Growth Opportunities	0,041
SC ₂₁ : Optimized traffic management	0,04
SC ₂₅ : Dynamic and cooperative planner	0,039
SC ₃₃ : New business models	0,032

Global priorities indicate that the factors most crucial to the adoption of PoDIUM in descending order of importance are: Trustworthiness of messages (authenticity and integrity), Reliable Communications, Security and Privacy, RU detection and protection, Support heterogeneity of RUs, and Communication channels as well as Near real-time communications (low latency). Notably, the majority of the top 10 factors fall within the first two categories/criteria. This alignment underscores PoDIUM's core objectives, aiming to ensure the safety of passengers and RUs while enhancing their experience through the provision of advanced functionalities.

5. Conclusions

While the first commercial deployments of CCAM systems are underway, it is crucial to address and understand various challenges. The embryonic stage of these systems, coupled with the multi-disciplinary nature of impacting factors, adds complexity to the situation. Consequently, a well-defined roadmap encompassing technical, economic, regulatory, and other considerations is needed. Critical decisions should be highlighted within this roadmap, and a successful rollout strategy requires clearly defined business cases.

In this deliverable, we conducted an analysis of the current state of PoDIUM components in the market, identifying their characteristics and trends. Additionally, we performed an initial roadmapping exercise, addressing technological, techno-economic, standardization, and regulatory issues integral to a successful deployment strategy. Finally, we defined the ecosystem around the PoDIUM platform to guide the definition of profitable business models and cases.

Market analysis underscored the dynamic growth of all investigated markets in terms of revenues, market size, growth, and the number of players/competitors. The findings indicate that now is the opportune time to initiate the deployment of innovative solutions related to CCAM.

To assess factors influencing the market adoption and evolution of PoDIUM solutions, the AHP methodology was employed. Through discussions with experts, a hierarchy of the main objective was established, and criteria and sub-criteria were selected. A questionnaire was then distributed, and collected responses were processed and analyzed, leading to the following conclusions.

Basic PoDIUM features for enhanced system performance / capabilities are considered the most crucial criterion, followed by “CCAM Service Management Add-on features and Acceptance / Flexibility, with Business and Strategy” having the lowest weight. Among sub-criteria, the trustworthiness of messages (authenticity and integrity) ranked highest, followed by Reliable Communications, Security and Privacy, RU detection and protection as well as Support heterogeneity of RUs and comm channels. The emphasis on the Trustworthiness of messages (authenticity and integrity) as well as on security and reliability issues can be attributed to the critical and sensitive nature of the CCAM system.

An analysis of the PoDIUM ecosystem was also conducted, defining involved actors, identifying new players, and describing their relations along with revenue streams.

The deliverable aims to provide initial insights into the business aspects of PoDIUM and CCAM in general, serving as guidance for PoDIUM partners and other stakeholders interested in CCAM systems rollout. Beyond investment strategies, efforts should focus on increasing awareness of the benefits arising from such systems. Finally, though regulatory as well as market-related issues might not be among the top preferences of experts, relevant aspects should be seriously considered, as they can significantly impact the success of CCAM systems.

6. References

- [1] <https://www.maximizemarketresearch.com/market-report/connected-and-autonomous-mobility-vehicles-market/207417/>
- [2] <https://www.prnewswire.com/news-releases/2020-will-be-the-year-of-cooperative-mobility-via-the-connected-car-300980473.html>
- [3] <https://www.acumenresearchandconsulting.com/smart-mobility-market>
- [4] <https://www.kbvresearch.com/smart-mobility-market/>
- [5] <https://www.alliedmarketresearch.com/connected-car-market>
- [6] <https://www.thebrainyinsights.com/report/connected-vehicle-market-13487>
- [7] <https://www.precedenceresearch.com/connected-cars-market>
- [8] <https://www.mckinsey.com/industries/automotive-and-assembly/our-insights/autonomous-drivings-future-convenient-and-connected>
- [9] <https://straitresearch.com/report/autonomous-vehicle-market>
- [10] <https://straitresearch.com/press-release/global-intelligent-transportation-systems-market-size>
- [11] <https://www.prnewswire.com/news-releases/intelligent-transportation-systems-market-size-worth--96-68-billion-globally-by-2030-at-6-7-cagr-verified-market-research-301549014.html>
- [12] <https://www.alliedmarketresearch.com/intelligent-transportation-system-market>
- [13] https://www.reportlinker.com/p06192189/Intelligent-transportation-system-market-Segmented-by-system-by-application-and-Region-Global-Analysis-of-Market-Size-Share-Trends-for-and-Forecasts-to.html?utm_source=GNW
- [14] L. Liang, H. Peng, G. Y. Li, and X. Shen, "Vehicular communications: A physical layer perspective," *IEEE Trans. Veh. Technol.*, vol. 66, no. 12, pp. 10647–10659, Dec. 2017.
- [15] <https://www.thebusinessresearchcompany.com/report/v2v-communication-global-market-report>
- [16] <https://www.einpresswire.com/article/625301732/dsrc-technology-market-is-poised-to-value-over-usd-9-3-bn-by-2032-cagr-13-9>
- [17] Business Growth Reports, "Global C-V2X Technology Market Overview" [2023]
- [18] <https://www.grandviewresearch.com/industry-analysis/digital-twin-market#:~:text=Report%20Overview,the%20physical%20and%20virtual%20worlds>
- [19] <https://www.fortunebusinessinsights.com/digital-twin-market-106246#:~:text=The%20global%20digital%20twin%20market,XR%29%2C%20and>
- [20] <https://www.marketsandmarkets.com/Market-Reports/digital-twin-market-225269522.html#:~:text=DOWNLOAD%20PDF,increasing%20focus%20on%20predictive%20maintenance>
- [21] <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1296187/global-digital-twin-market-by-industry/#:~:text=Mar%2017%2C%202022,By%202025>

- [22]<https://www.mordorintelligence.com/industry-reports/digital-twin-market#:~:text=Digital%20Twin%20Market%20Size%20%26,Pacific%20%28China%2C%20Japan>
- [23]<https://www.marketsandmarkets.com/Market-Reports/digital-twin-market-225269522.html#:~:text=DOWNLOAD%20PDF,increasing%20focus%20on%20predictive%20maintenance>
- [24]<https://www.skyquestt.com/report/digital-twin-market#:~:text=Digital%20Twin%20Market%20Analysis%20by,computing%2C%20internet%20of%20things%2C>
- [25]<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2667241323000137#:~:text=Digital%20Twin%20applications%20are%20widely,forecasting%2C%20and%20vehicle%20flaw%20identification>
- [26]M. Singh, R. Srivastava, E Fuenmayor, V. Kuts Y. Qiao, N. Murray, D. Devine, Applications of Digital Twin across Industries: A Review. Applied Sciences. 2022; 12(11):5727. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app12115727>
- [27]<https://www.acumenresearchandconsulting.com/digital-twin-market>
- [28]<https://www.plm.automation.siemens.com/global/it/our-story/glossary/digital-twin/24465>
- [29]<https://5gmeta-project.eu/>
- [30]<https://www.thebusinessresearchcompany.com/report/mmwave-5g-global-market-report>
- [31]<https://www.emergenresearch.com/industry-report/millimeter-wave-fifth-generation-market>
- [32]<https://www.whiteboxsolution.com/blog/wi-fi-6-vs-5g-mmwave/>
- [33]<https://www.5gtechnologyworld.com/5g-mmwave-test-builds-on-rf-best-practices/>
- [34]E. Kampert, C. Schettler, R. Woodman, P. A. Jennings, and M. D. Higgins, "Millimeter-wave communication for a last-mile autonomous transport vehicle," IEEE Access, vol. 8, pp. 8386–8392, 2020
- [35]I. Rasheed and F. Hu, "Intelligent super-fast vehicle-to-everything 5g communications with predictive switching between mmwave and thz links," Vehicular Communications, vol. 27, p. 100303, 2021.
- [36]https://transport.ec.europa.eu/transport-themes/intelligent-transport-systems/cooperative-connected-and-automated-mobility-ccam_en
- [37]https://www.nks-kem.de/aktuelles/news/offene_konsultation_ccam_loesungen_in_europa
- [38]<https://qualcomm.ft.com/article/5g-cities-of-the-future>
- [39]S. Jaswal, D. Yadav, D. P. Bhatt and M. Tiwari, "mmWave technology: An impetus for smart city initiatives," 2nd Smart Cities Symposium (SCS 2019), Bahrain, Bahrain, 2019, pp. 1-4, doi: 10.1049/cp.2019.0203.
- [40]<https://www.hindawi.com/journals/js/2021/8199361/>
- [41]<https://www.theinsightpartners.com/reports/data-fusion-market/>
- [42]<https://www.futuremarketinsights.com/reports/sensor-fusion-market>
- [43]<https://www.futuremarketinsights.com/reports/trusted-platform-module-tpm-market>
- [44]<https://www.verifiedmarketresearch.com/product/trusted-platform-module-tpm-market/>

- [45]<https://trustedcomputinggroup.org/work-groups/vehicle-services/>
- [46]<https://getcruise.com/>
- [47]<https://www.navya.tech/en/>
- [48]<https://waymo.com/>
- [49]<https://nauto.com/>
- [50]<https://easymile.com/>
- [51]<http://www.stanley-robotics.com/>
- [52]<https://www.alba-robot.com/>
- [53]<https://www.slamcore.com/>
- [54]https://www.dspace.com/en/pub/home/products/sw/experimentandvisualization/aurelion_sensor-realistic_sim.cfm
- [55]<https://www.mathworks.com/products/sensor-fusion-and-tracking.html>
- [56]<http://www.baselabs.de/>
- [57]<https://www.ertrac.org/news/new-ertrac-ccam-roadmap/>
- [58]<https://5gaa.org/>
- [59]<https://www.prnewswire.com/news-releases/edge-computing-market-worth-111-3-billion-by-2028---exclusive-report-by-marketsandmarkets-301869421.html>
- [60]<https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/edge-computing-market-size-share-growth-drivers-industry/>
- [61]https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/A-9-2021-0211_EN.html
- [62]<https://networkbuilders.intel.com/intel-technologies/intel-smart-edge/commercial-applications>
- [63]https://portal.5gasp.eu/services/services_marketplace
- [64]N. Ghafoorianfar and M. Roopaei, "Environmental Perception in Autonomous Vehicles Using Edge Level Situational Awareness," 2020 10th Annual Computing and Communication Workshop and Conference (CCWC), Las Vegas, NV, USA, 2020, pp. 0444-0448, doi: 10.1109/CCWC47524.2020.9031155
- [65]H. Chen, S. Chan-Olmsted, J. Kim, and I. Mayor Sanabria (2022), "Consumers' perception on artificial intelligence applications in marketing communication", Qualitative Market Research, Vol. 25 No. 1, pp. 125-142. <https://doi.org/10.1108/QMR-03-2021-0040>
- [66]F. Rosique, P.J. Navarro, C. Fernández, A. Padilla, A Systematic Review of Perception System and Simulators for Autonomous Vehicles Research. Sensors 2019, 19, 648. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s19030648>
- [67]T. L. Saaty, "A scaling method for priorities in hierarchical structures," Journal of Mathematical Psychology, vol. 15, pp. 234-281, 1977
- [68]A. M. A. Bahurmoz, "The analytic hierarchy process at DarAl-Hekma, Saudi Arabia," Interfaces, vol. 33, pp. 70-78, 2003.
- [69] A. Kengpol and C. O'Brien, "The development of a decision support tool for the selection of advanced technology to achieve rapid product development," International Journal of Production Economics, vol. 69, pp. 177-191, 2001.

- [70] G. Noci and G. Toletti, "Selecting quality-based programmes in small firms: A comparison between the fuzzy linguistic approach and the analytic hierarchy process," *International Journal of Production Economics*, vol. 67, pp. 113-133, 2000.
- [71] M. M. Albayrakoglu, "Justification of New Manufacturing Technology: A Strategic Approach Using the Analytical Hierarchy Process," *Production and Inventory Management Journal*, First Quarter, vol. 37, pp. 71-76, 1996.
- [72] T. L. Saaty, *The analytic hierarchy process: planning, priority setting, resource allocation*. New York: McGraw-Hill International Book Co., 1980.
- [73] G. Dede, et al., "Towards a Roadmap for Future Home Networking Systems: An Analytical Hierarchy Process Approach," *IEEE Systems Journal*, vol. 5, pp. 374-384, 2011.
- [74] G. Dede, et al., "Evaluation of Optical Wireless Technologies in Home Networking: An Analytical Hierarchy Process Approach," *IEEE/OSA Journal of Optical Communications and Networking*, vol. 3, pp. 850-859, 2011.
- [75] S. Nikou, et al., "Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) Approach for Selecting Mobile Service Category (Consumers' Preferences)," in *2011 10th International Conference on Mobile Business*, 2011, pp. 119-128.
- [76] S. Qingyang and A. Jamalipour, "Network selection in an integrated wireless LAN and UMTS environment using mathematical modeling and computing techniques," *IEEE Wireless Communications*, vol. 12, pp. 42-48, 2005.
- [77] T. L. Saaty and M. S. Ozdemir, "Why the magic number seven plus or minus two," *Mathematical and Computer Modelling*, vol. 38, pp. 233-244, 2003.
- [78] G. Dede, et al., "Convergence properties and practical estimation of the probability of rank reversal in pairwise comparisons for multi-criteria decision making problems," *European Journal of Operational Research*, vol. 241, pp. 458-468, 2015.
- [79] G. Dede, et al., "Theoretical estimation of the probability of weight rank reversal in pairwise comparisons," *European Journal of Operational Research*, vol. 252, pp. 587- 600, 2016.